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Doctoral Dissertation

The nexus between climate change mitigation and development in Laos

submitted by

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Affidavit

I hereby declare that I have authored this dissertation independently, and that I have not used any assistance other than that which is permitted. The work contained herein is my own except where explicitly stated otherwise. All ideas taken in wording or in basic content from unpublished sources or from published literature are duly identified and cited, and the precise references included. Any contribution from colleagues is explicitly stated in the authorship statement of the published papers.

I further declare that this dissertation has not been submitted, in whole or in part, in the same or a similar form, to any other educational institution as part of the requirements for an academic degree.

I hereby confirm that I am familiar with the standards of Scientific Integrity and with the guidelines of Good Scientific Practice, and that this work fully complies with these standards and guidelines.

Vienna, August 2023

Sonja BAUERNSCHUSTER (*manu propria*)

“I wish it need not have happened in my time,” said Frodo.

“So do I,” said Gandalf, “and so do all who live to see such times. But that is not for them to decide. All we have to decide is what to do with the time that is given us.”

J.R.R. Tolkien, *The Fellowship of the Ring*

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Preface

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List of publications

- I. **Bauernschuster, S.**, Pichler, M., Ingalls, M., Thongmanivong, S., & Gingrich, S. (2022). Discursive and biophysical dimensions of land sparing policies in Laos: Implications for greenhouse gas emissions and food security. *Land Use Policy*, 120, 106293. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2022.106293>

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Abstract

Land provides diverse services to human societies, including food production and carbon sequestration for climate change mitigation. Balancing *competing* land uses is crucial to avoid detrimental trade-offs for both land users and ecosystems. This thesis provides insights on a balancing strategy known as land sparing (LS), which aims to reduce the land required for farming, and preserve the thus spared land for nature conservation, all while ensuring food security remains unaffected. The thesis comprises two studies on land-use change (LUC) in Laos, a least developed country in the Southeast Asian tropics that has been actively pursuing LS in recent years. In these studies, my colleagues and I quantify ecosystem carbon fluxes induced by LUC in Laos between 2000 and 2020. Chapter 1 presents socio-economic and environmental narratives underlying the LS objective in official Lao land-use strategies. We contrast found narratives with some of their biophysical dimensions such as nation-wide LUC, associated greenhouse gas emissions and sinks, as well as agricultural production and emissions and certain food security indicators. Chapter 2 zooms in to the Lao land-concession landscape in order to quantify climate effects of concession-related LUC between 2001 and 2017. Utilizing an interdisciplinary approach, my research identifies narratives concerning alleged drawbacks of shifting cultivation compared to the potential benefits of tree plantations and intensified agriculture, and demonstrates through a comprehensive, multi-dimensional biophysical analysis that these narratives oversimplify reality. The importance of location choices of concessions becomes clear in order for them to support rather than impede climate change mitigation and socially just development. The findings serve as an invitation both to the scientific and political communities to embrace a holistic approach when addressing the nexus between climate change mitigation and development.

Kurzfassung

Land erbringt für Menschen vielfältige Leistungen, etwa die Produktion von Nahrung oder die Bindung von Kohlenstoff zur Bekämpfung der Klimakrise. *Konkurrierende* Landnutzungen müssen ausgeglichen werden, um Zielkonflikte zwischen Landnutzer*innen und Ökosystemen zu vermeiden. Die vorliegende Dissertation gibt Einblicke in „Land Sparing“ (LS), eine Landnutzungsstrategie, die durch reduzierten Flächenbedarf von Hohertrags-Landwirtschaft Flächen für Naturschutz bereitstellen und gleichzeitig zu Ernährungssicherheit beitragen soll. Meine Arbeit umfasst zwei Studien zu Landnutzungsveränderungen (land-use change = LUC) in Laos, einem der am wenigsten entwickelten Länder in den südostasiatischen Tropen, das in den vergangenen Jahren aktiv LS angestrebt hat. In beiden Studien quantifizieren meine Kolleg*innen und ich Kohlenstoffflüsse, die durch LUC in Ökosystemen zwischen 2000 und 2020 in Laos verursacht wurden. Die erste Studie identifiziert sozio-ökonomische und Umweltschutz-Narrative, die der LS-Zielsetzung in laotischen Landnutzungsstrategien zugrunde liegen. Diesen Narrativen stelle ich einige ihrer inhärenten biophysischen Dimensionen gegenüber, wie landesweite LUCs, damit einhergehende Treibhausgasflüsse, landwirtschaftliche Produktion und Emissionen und diverse Indikatoren zur Ernährungssicherheit. Die zweite Studie fokussiert auf Klimaeffekte durch Konzessionen in Laos zwischen 2001 und 2017. Durch den interdisziplinären Ansatz meiner Arbeit können Narrative zur Schädlichkeit von Wanderfeldbau und Erwartungen an intensivierte Landwirtschaft und Baumpflanzungen identifiziert und mittels multidimensionaler, biophysischer Analyse als übermäßig vereinfacht erwiesen werden. Die Relevanz der Standortwahl von Konzessionen wird deutlich, damit diese Klimaschutz und gerechte Entwicklung fördern statt zu behindern. Die Ergebnisse laden wissenschaftlich wie politisch zu einer ganzheitlichen Herangehensweise an Fragen im Nexus zwischen Klimaschutz und Entwicklung ein.

The nexus between climate change mitigation and
development in Laos

1. Land-use change induced carbon fluxes in Lao PDR between 2000 and 2020 in the realm of climate and food crises

1. Trends of land-use competition between food production and land-based carbon removal – globally, in Southeast Asia, and in the Lao PDR

Global trends show the importance of (primary) forests for climate change mitigation, but also indicate scarcity of available land for land-based measures with severe implications for food security, among others.

The use of land has always been essential for human livelihoods and well-being, with different landscapes serving diverse societal demands, including food production, housing, and cultural activities (Ellis et al., 2019). Consequently, with over 75% of the Earth's terrestrial surface currently being used or managed for human needs, competition for land has intensified (ibid.). Global demand for land-based products and services has escalated so that now there is a significant gap between e.g. the land required for future agricultural production and the land available for such purposes, with climate change mitigation measures further exacerbating this gap (Dooley et al., 2022; Haberl, 2015; Meyfroidt et al., 2022). For instance, Dooley et al. (2022) highlight that meeting projected biological carbon removal in national climate commitments would require approximately 1.2 billion hectares of land, equivalent to the current extent of cropland, which is highly impractical. Balancing the needs of various actors equitably while avoiding overexploitation of ecosystems is essential yet highly challenging and often results in trade-offs between people and nature, and in conflicts over land (Meyfroidt et al., 2022; Müller et al., 2016; Turner et al., 2021). The climate crisis adds to the difficulty to sustainably improve human development (Fuso Nerini et al., 2019).

Competition for land is particularly acute in developing countries, where climate change, land degradation, population growth, and the frequent need to (over-)exploit natural resources to mitigate poverty often add to the pressures on agricultural production. A global food crisis is looming in the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic, the war in Ukraine, and more frequent climate-related shocks, leading to over 800 million persons worldwide suffering from hunger in 2021, with rising tendency (UN, 2022). Sustainable intensification of agricultural production is essential to simultaneously enhance food production and reduce emissions associated with agriculture, with less need to expand agricultural land (Dooley et al., 2022).

Reducing emissions is especially significant given that agriculture and related land-use emissions account for approximately one-fourth of total greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from global economic activities (Tubiello, 2019) and thus significantly contribute to climate change. Limiting global warming to 1.5 degrees Celsius, as set as goal under the Paris

Agreement in 2015 (UNFCCC, 2016), requires not only *reducing* emissions but also *removing* GHGs from the atmosphere. In this context, the most relevant option today is related to land use and includes measures such as afforestation, reforestation, and ecosystem restoration, particularly on land that has not been forested recently (Fuss et al., 2018; Roe et al., 2019; Smith et al., 2019). Depending on the extent and management of afforestation areas after establishment, they can provide a range of services and functions parallel to carbon sequestration, such as the production of food, fuels, and fiber, regulation of water services and air quality, and habitat for biodiversity, as well as societal services such as jobs and recreation, and thereby might alleviate land-use competition (Smith et al., 2019).

Forest transitions take place *inter alia* in Southeast Asia. This can be favorable for the climate, but poses the risk of increased food insecurity and environmental injustices.

In this light, "forest transitions" have received much attention, particularly with the prospect that transitions from net deforestation to forest recovery observed in several temperate, subtropical, and boreal zones could be replicated in tropical countries, initiating a global forest transition (Kull, 2017; Rudel et al., 2020). It is well established that tropical rainforests have a greater capacity to sequester carbon from the atmosphere than temperate or boreal forests, making it crucial to protect the remaining rainforests from further destruction, and restore or expand tropical forests to mitigate climate change (Estoque et al., 2019; Harris et al., 2021). In Southeast Asia, hosting 15% of global tropical rainforests, forests are under immense pressure and declining at catastrophic rates in some countries, while others maintained or increased forest cover in recent years (Harris et al., 2021; Southworth et al., 2012; Stibig et al., 2014). Countries that have experienced forest transitions in this region are for example Vietnam, the Philippines, Thailand and China (while not traditionally considered part of Southeast Asia, the southern region of China falls within the Southeast Asian biogeographic region)(de Jong et al., 2017; Pichler et al., 2021a).

Countries that only recently experienced a forest transition likely underwent what Rudel et al. (2020) call the "latecomer effect": forest expansion - in contrast to forest transitions in the nineteenth and twentieth centuries - occurred intentionally, initiated by governments eager to halt deforestation before its detrimental effects observed in other countries could become effective. While a global forest transition might help tackling the climate crisis and is therefore of high priority in international climate agreements and programs (e.g., the "UN REDD +" framework (<https://redd.unfccc.int/>), the "One trillion trees" campaign initiated by the World Economic Forum (<https://www.1t.org/>), or the "Great Green Wall of the Sahara and the Sahel Initiative" by the African Union (<https://thegreatgreenwall.org/>)), other problems aggravate. There is for example a high risk of environmental injustices and conflicts if afforestation or restoration efforts take place on land that, contrary to common claims, is neither degraded nor unused, but instead utilized by marginalized communities, who then face displacement and impoverishment (Sovacool, 2021). This phenomenon is also known as "green grabbing" (Fairhead et al., 2012). Consequently, exploring forest transitions requires researchers to not

only consider changes in forest cover and quality, but keep socio-ecological relationships between people and land, discourses, values and perceptions around forests in mind (Kull, 2017).

Agricultural production in the Lao PDR occurs within both cropland and forests. Governmental efforts to facilitate a forest transition resulted in increasingly segregated landscapes and aggravated land scarcity for (poorer) local land users while failing to initiate a forest transition.

When I began my PhD in 2019, FAOSTAT data indicated an increase in forest cover in the Lao PDR (hereafter called Laos), positioning it among the Southeast Asian nations that had undergone a forest transition. However, subsequent data revisions and personal conversations with representatives from conservation organizations and local data scientists indicated that forest decline was ongoing. This was confirmed by national data published later and subsequently updated FAO data, which now show decreasing trends in forest cover in favor of the expansion of cropland.

The forest decline in Laos contradicts the Lao government's target of achieving 70% forest cover (GoL, 2005), a goal enshrined in numerous policy documents. Laos, as a "latecomer country", is attempting to initiate a forest transition, because i) it witnessed the severe consequences of deforestation in neighboring countries such as Thailand, Vietnam and South China, including biodiversity loss, wood scarcity, import dependency, or severe flooding (ICEM, 2003); ii), forest increase has been associated with economic benefits through initiatives like REDD+ and green development programs (GoL, 2011). And iii), forest protection is considered to align well with the eradication of poverty, as it implies the eradication or stabilization of shifting cultivation. Shifting cultivation is a traditional agricultural practice that involves clearing forested plots for crop cultivation and leaving them fallow to regenerate before using them again (Epprecht et al., 2018; Évrard and Baird, 2017; Ingalls et al., 2018b). The practice was often connoted by policy makers as a major cause of deforestation, environmental degradation, and impoverishment (Suhardiman et al., 2019). Therefore, like other countries in Southeast Asia, the Lao government has for decades attempted to diminish or stabilize this form of land use in order to protect forests, stimulate alternative, more productive agricultural practices, facilitate economic development, and exert greater control over remote populations that may pose a subversive threat (Baird and Shoemaker, 2007; Lestrelin et al., 2012; Padoch et al., 2007).

The government's territorial strategies have resulted in increasingly segregated landscapes, with protected natural habitats on the one hand and intensive agriculture on the other, in contrast to the complex and integrated mosaic landscapes associated with shifting cultivation (Castella et al., 2013). These strategies have exhibited contrasting effects on households of different socioeconomic backgrounds, with wealthier households benefitting from new opportunities while poorer households experiencing a reduction in land access. However, the strategies have not stimulated the envisaged increase of forest cover (Castella et al., 2013; Ducourtieux, 2005; Lestrelin et al., 2012; Suhardiman et al., 2019).

2. Land users in Laos – the government, smallholder farmers, and investors

The government exercises ownership over all natural resources and exerts control over individuals and their behaviors through the establishment of geographical delineations, the exclusion of certain groups from certain areas, and the imposition of regulations that either permit or prohibit specific activities within the confines of these boundaries.

The Constitution of Laos explicitly designates the central government as the caretaker and manager of all natural resources within the country (Fujita and Phengsopha, 2008). Laos aspires to enhance livelihoods, alleviate poverty, and achieve graduation from its least developed status primarily by tapping its natural resources. Its function as caretaker of natural resources has empowered the Lao government to undertake various initiatives in this regard over the past decades. These include a large-scale internal resettlement program in the 1970s, the establishment of land zoning, classification, and allocation systems in the 1990s, and the introduction of land titling to facilitate land commercialization in the late 1990s (Lestrelin et al., 2012). As a result of these efforts, approximately half of Laos' population has experienced displacement or resettlement, territorial boundaries have been delineated, and different types of forestlands (such as conservation, production, and protection forestland) as well as non-forestland have been officially designated, regardless of the actual land cover. 70% of the country's area has been classified (not assessed!) as state forestland, imposing restrictions or exclusions on agricultural activities (MRLG, 2019; Pichler et al., 2021b).

Small-scale and subsistence farmers make up approximately 60% of the Lao population and are heavily affected by such land-use plans and programs.

Approximately 3000 villages are situated within the aforementioned state forestlands, while many others are adjacent to them, encompassing agricultural and other types of lands (MRLG, 2019). Land dispossession, displacement, and tenure insecurity are particularly pronounced in areas predominantly characterized by customary and communal lands, as well as indigenous and ethnic minority populations (Kenney-Lazar et al., 2022). The restrictions imposed on forest access have resulted in the deprivation of essential resources such as food, fuel wood, medicinal products, and other non-timber forest products (NTFPs), which are vital for the subsistence and economic activities of local land users, particularly shifting cultivators who heavily rely on extensive land for fallowing (Broegaard et al., 2017; Ingalls et al., 2018b). In Laos, the majority of households (60%) were engaged in agriculture as of 2019/20, with approximately 22-33% of the total production area dedicated to shifting cultivation (Ingalls et al., 2018b; Lao Statistics Bureau, 2021; Chen et al., 2023). The mountainous and steep terrain of Laos, coupled with the presence of unexploded ordnances from the Indochinese conflicts of the 1960s and 70s, pose constraints on the availability of arable land for agriculture (Ingalls et al., 2018b). The scarcity of available land has compelled local land users to adopt intensified land-use practices, resulting in frequent land degradation and subsequent reductions in agricultural yields. Consequently, affected households have experienced heightened levels of

food insecurity and an increased reliance on cash crop production and wage labor for their sustenance (Boillat et al., 2015; Fujita and Phengsopha, 2008). The combination of high food and energy prices, shortages of essential goods like fuel and agricultural inputs, and escalating agricultural production costs, such as the significant price hikes of livestock inputs (up to 300%) and the tripling of rice production costs in 2022 compared to 2021, creates immense challenges for smallholder farmers who rely on external inputs (WFP and FAO, 2022).

Domestic and foreign investors are also competing for land.

State-land concessions in Laos emerged as part of the country's transition from a centralized, state-socialist economy to a neoliberal economic framework. In 1992, foreign investors were allowed to acquire leases or concessions for state land. Initially, the number of land concessions granted was limited, but in the early 2000s, their numbers and size significantly increased due to high prices of resource commodities and the government's intention to "turn land into capital" (Kenney-Lazar et al., 2018). Since then, the government has issued state-land concessions exceeding one million hectares, which represents approximately 5% of the national territory. These concessions and leases have been allocated to both domestic and foreign investors for various projects, such as hydropower, mining, agriculture, and industrial tree plantations (Schönweger, 2012).

The majority of investments in terms of quantity (60% of all deals) are domestic, followed by foreign deals (32%) and joint ventures (8%). However, when considering the granted area, foreign deals account for 61% of the total, indicating that foreign investments have a substantially larger impact on domestic land resources than domestic investments (Hett et al., 2020).

Initially, powerful regional and domestic investors overrode local interests and land governance mechanisms. However, as available land became scarcer and local actors became more experienced in dealing with land acquisitions, these investments tended to encounter failures or transition towards more inclusive and bottom-up investment models (Baird, 2020; Messerli et al., 2015). The social and environmental implications of land acquisitions have been well documented over the past decade, demonstrating how they dispossess people of their customary lands and resources, pollute surrounding environments, and provide little economic opportunity in the form of wage labor (Kenney-Lazar et al., 2018). However, they have also provided a channel for smallholders to turn their land into capital and their customary rights over it into a territorial strategy to secure their land tenure (Kramp et al., 2022). For instance, farmers who have historically faced difficulties in getting government institutions to recognize their land tenure were able to secure the latter through rubber cultivation (Kramp et al., 2022).

Against this background, this dissertation inquires the following general question: How has Laos approached the issue of land competition within the nexus between climate change mitigation and socio-economic development?

2. Conceptual basis of the thesis

This thesis is firmly grounded in the Vienna School of Social Ecology, which has served as the theoretical foundation throughout my Master's and PhD programs in the past 9 years. Numerous concepts and methodologies that I have acquired during this extensive period of study inform my research, both explicitly and implicitly (Haberl et al., 2016b). Additionally, I have integrated approaches from the fields of Land System Sciences and Political Ecology in my research, allowing for a multidimensional perspective.

1. Exploring land use from the perspectives of Social Ecology and Land System Sciences

Social Ecology is an interdisciplinary research field rooted in the traditions of Social Sciences, the Humanities and Natural Sciences. Social Ecologists symmetrically address and recognize the interconnectedness of cultural/societal spheres and natural/material spheres, viewing them as co-evolving through diverse interactions (Haberl et al., 2019; Fischer-Kowalski and Erb, 2016). This implies that societies not only actively and intentionally shape the natural environment to serve human purposes but also continuously adapt to environmental conditions, including those influenced by their own actions over centuries (Fischer-Kowalski and Weisz, 2016). Particularly the biophysical structures of societies (humans, livestock and artifacts) thrive and persist through the deliberate exchange of energy, material, work and information flows between social and natural systems, which is referred to as "social metabolism" (Fischer-Kowalski and Erb, 2016). Unintentional outcomes and feedbacks across multiple levels and scales are not unusual given the complexities of social-ecological systems (Schlüter et al., 2022).

Social Ecology employs the concept of "colonization" to capture organized social interventions (e.g. farming) that aim at enhancing nature's usefulness for society and lead to deliberate and lasting alterations of natural systems (e.g. agricultural systems) (Fischer-Kowalski and Weisz, 1999). A successful colonizing intervention involves two essential components (Fischer-Kowalski and Weisz, 1999): firstly, it must have tangible effects in the physical world (e.g., changing characteristics of systems before and after the intervention, such as carbon stocks in croplands after forest conversions (Haberl et al., 2016a)), and secondly, it must be culturally conceived, organized, and monitored to be meaningful in the realm of communication (e.g., interventions aimed at sustainable development, an objective shared by many). In my research I focus on the societal **use of land** in Laos in the nexus between economic development and climate change mitigation. Land use with the societal purpose to produce food, extract resources, and sequester carbon falls under the concept of colonization. Sustainability issues can manifest either on the input side (nature → society), wherein certain societal needs cannot be met by the natural system (e.g., food scarcity), or on the output side (society → nature), when absorption or carrying capacities of the natural system are reached

(e.g., GHG emissions in the atmosphere)(Fischer-Kowalski and Haberl, 1997). The concept of colonization illustrates my understanding of land use as societal intervention into natural processes and the emergence of certain ecological services and disservices across various levels and scales.

While Social Ecology encompasses a broad range of interactions between society and nature, my research specifically focuses on land use, making it closely aligned with the principles of **Land System Sciences (LSS)**. Several conceptual frameworks utilized in my study are drawn from this particular field of research. LSS is dedicated to studying land systems and their dynamic processes, encompassing, as Social Ecology, the complex interactions between human activities and the environment (Verburg et al., 2015). The main objectives of LSS are to comprehend the drivers, state, trends, and impacts of different land systems on social and natural processes. This includes exploring the trade-offs and synergies that arise from changes within the land system and their implications within the broader social-ecological system. Additionally, LSS aims to contribute to the development of pathways towards sustainability for both human societies and the natural environment (De Bremond, 2021; Turner et al., 2021). One significant focus within LSS is the mapping of land-system changes, particularly in terms of land-use and land-cover changes. LSS also includes investigating phenomena such as ecosystem services, land-atmosphere processes, land governance, and urban-rural teleconnections (Scheidel and Gingrich, 2020; Verburg et al., 2015). Many LSS and social-ecological concepts are explored in my thesis, including the "land sparing/ land sharing"¹ approaches, the complexities of land-use competition and associated trade-offs, the dynamics of land-use intensification, the broader patterns of LUC, and the environmental and social implications related to forest transformations.

Given the ever-increasing demand for land-based services, the finite nature of land and its already extensive utilization, two primary alternatives for future land use are deemed reasonable: land-use intensification, aiming to maximize productivity on existing land, and the emergence of land scarcity or land-use competition, necessitating the allocation and management of limited land resources.

2. Exploring land-use competition from the perspective of Political Ecology

Political Ecology (PE) has the potential to enrich social-ecological and LSS perspectives on land-use competition by providing critical research that examines land characteristics such as

¹ Proponents of the "land sparing" concept argue that higher yields on smaller land plots can spare land for nature conservation (Phalan, 2018). In contrast, the "land sharing" approach advocates for integrating agricultural production with conservation on the same land. This perspective emphasizes the use of agroecological practices that aim to mimic natural ecosystems, promoting biodiversity while also meeting food production needs. Critics argue that land sharing may result in lower agricultural productivity compared to land sparing, potentially exacerbating challenges related to food security. Increasingly, these scientific views have been depolarized, acknowledging that the roles of both shared and spared landscapes are context-dependent (Mertz and Mertens 2017).

tenure, access, and diverse forms of material and cultural land uses. It establishes connections between political processes and environmental outcomes, including conflicts and social injustices arising from LUC (Scheidel and Gingrich, 2020). Rooted in critical social sciences, PE focuses on power relations, conflicts, and justice concerns associated with specific resource uses (ibid.). PE aims to (re-)establish political dimensions within primarily apolitical discussions, thoughts, and investigations of ecological inquiries. It seeks to understand how power structures, societal discourses and narratives influence the manner in which societies engage with and impact their natural surroundings. With a critical lens, PE scrutinizes the competition and crises arising from social-ecological dynamics (Gottschlich et al., 2022).

From a PE perspective, **competition over natural resources** is influenced by power dynamics among actors with diverse interests. Due to power imbalances, not all actors are able to achieve their goals to the desired extent or benefit equally from LUC. It is therefore crucial to establish clear linkages between land and its users to understand conflicts arising from competing land-use claims (Scheidel and Gingrich, 2020). PE also recognizes that competition over land extends beyond human actors and encompasses discourses, policies, ideologies, and knowledge related to LUC (Niewöhner et al., 2016). As such, PE also examines how competing societal discourses and narratives about nature and its commodification influence local practices (ibid.).

3. My approach

In this thesis I combine approaches from Social Ecology, LSS, and PE to investigate multiple dimensions of LUC in Laos over a 20-year period. Using LSS methodologies, I analyze the impacts of LUC on ecosystem characteristics, specifically focusing on carbon stocks. My research focuses on the intricate dynamics of land-use competition, specifically examining the interactions between food production (Chapter 1), commercial exploitation (Chapter 2), and carbon sequestration. Implicitly drawing on concepts from Social Ecology and LSS, I examine the colonization of land and the provision of ecosystem services. Building on the insights of Scheidel and Gingrich (2020), I integrate approaches from LSS and PE, linking land to users and their interests, including shifting cultivators and large-scale land investors. Moreover, I conduct a Political-Ecological analysis of the narratives that shape the prevalent land-sparing paradigm in Lao land-use policies. This integration of knowledge from Social Ecology, LSS, and PE paves the way for well-informed research on land use that promotes ecological sustainability and social justice.

4. Key terms

Working in interdisciplinary fields such as Social Ecology, LSS, and PE necessitates the precise definition and clarification of terms used. Due to the chapters' character limitations, I could only provide a brief mention of certain terms without fully explaining and contextualizing them. However, in this Introduction, I aim to engage in a comprehensive discussion of these

key terms and elaborate on how I addressed the varying definitions employed by different actors such as the FAO, the Government of Laos, and researchers in diverse contexts.

Forest definitions are essential for operationalizing and monitoring changes in forest characteristics, such as deforestation, forest degradation, restoration, and reforestation. A broad range of definitions features a nuanced thinking about landscapes and can impact ideas, perceptions, and actions related to forest use and management (Kull, 2017; Scheidel and Gingrich, 2020). Depending on the specific context, "[...] forests can be seen as a source of timber products, an ecosystem composed of trees along with myriad forms of biological diversity, a home for indigenous people, a repository for carbon storage, a source of multiple ecosystem services, and as social-ecological systems, or as all of the above" (Chazdon et al., 2016, p. 539). Embracing this diversity is crucial when analyzing and interpreting forest phenomena, as well as discourses and visions related to the purpose of forests. In this thesis, I encounter divergent forest definitions by the FAO and the Lao Department of Forestry, resulting in varying data outcomes for spatio-temporal trends and forest-cover levels (see Figure 2 in Chapter 1, Bauernschuster, Pichler, Ingalls, et al. (2022)). Moreover, I follow the Lao Forest Monitoring (<https://nfms.dof.maf.gov.la/>) to differentiate between six distinct forest categories, and refer to the inventory on "Land leases and concessions in the Lao PDR" by Hett et al. (2020) to distinguish between the three most common tree plantation categories. These categories vary in terms of tree species composition and other ecological characteristics, such as carbon stocks. Lastly, I disentangle *land use* in contrast to *land cover* in co-existing environmental and socio-economic narratives underlying Lao land-use policies, such as the Forestry Strategy to the year 2020 (GoL, 2005) and Socio-economic Development Plans (GoL, 2006, 2016). A singular forest category would fail to capture the complexity of forest processes in Laos.

Another term subject to various interpretations is that of the land-use category "**regenerating vegetation**". It refers to fallow areas in shifting cultivation systems and is classified as forest land in Lao land-use documents such as National Forest Inventories or reports for REDD+ (DoF, 2018, 2020; DoF and JICA, 2017). Although these fallows temporarily fall below a certain vegetation threshold, it is expected that they will naturally recover into fully stocked forests over time (DoF, 2018). The ecological characteristics of fallows, such as aboveground carbon stocks (but not soil organic carbon stocks, as shown by Bruun et al. (2021)), biodiversity, and hydrology, are influenced by rotation intensities or fallow periods (Mertz et al., 2021; Ziegler et al., 2009). Shifting cultivation fallows serve as habitats for numerous species of non-timber forest products, wild food, rice, medicinal plants, and also provide grazing areas, thus playing a vital role for household food security, nutrition and income (Broegaard et al., 2017; Ingalls et al., 2018a). Given the limited available alternatives, I follow the classification of the land-use category 'regenerating vegetation' as synonym for shifting cultivation fallows, treating it as an additional category alongside forests. In doing so, I consider the various uses of these areas by local communities. The limited knowledge of the precise duration of fallow periods

poses constraints on the robustness of the findings presented in this thesis (see Appendix 3 of Chapter 2, Bauernschuster, Pichler, Nanhthavong, et al. (2022)).

Ecosystem services (ES) encompass the diverse array of benefits and functions provided by ecosystems to support the well-being and survival of natural and human systems (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). These services are categorized into four main types: provisioning, regulating, supporting, and cultural services. ES are intricately interconnected and interdependent, creating a complex network of interactions between ecosystems and society. They serve as a crucial foundation for environmental management and sustainable decision-making. However, the recognition, valuation, and utilization of specific ES are influenced by varying interests, often leading to conflicting perspectives (Kull et al., 2015). In real-world contexts, diverse actors mobilize the concept and tool of ES, resulting in regionally specific, politically nuanced outcomes (ibid.). The concept of ES is implicitly used in this thesis to document the applied focus in the analyzed land-use policies, such as the Forestry Strategy to the year 2020 (GoL, 2005) and socio-economic development plans (GoL, 2006, 2016). Other ES beyond food production and carbon sequestration, as well as the broader concept of nature's contribution to people, which encompasses both positive and negative contributions and integrates social and cultural values, indigenous knowledge systems, and complex trade-offs, lie outside the scope of this research (Ellis et al., 2019; IPBES, 2019).

Food security refers to the state in which all individuals have equitable and sustainable physical, social, and economic access to adequate, safe, and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and preferences (FAO, 2008). It encompasses multiple dimensions, namely availability, accessibility, utilization, and stability, which must be simultaneously fulfilled for true food security to be achieved (ibid.). Various factors, including agricultural productivity, food distribution systems, market dynamics, trade policies, land-tenure security, and social safety nets, influence the attainment of food security (Castella et al., 2023; Gingrich et al., 2015; Hepp et al., 2019; Keovilignavong and Suhardiman, 2020). In Chapter 1 of this thesis (Bauernschuster et al., 2022a), we focus on investigating food security indicators specifically related to the physical access to food. To conduct this analysis, we utilize indicators sourced from FAOSTAT. However, it should be noted that the examination of food sovereignty, a complementary concept that emphasizes social justice, cultural identity, and the rights and aspirations of individuals, communities, and nations to define and control their own food systems, falls beyond the scope of this research (Wittman, 2011).

Concessions or land acquisitions, used interchangeably in this thesis, pertain to government-owned land granted to domestic and foreign investors for an agreed period of time (Hett et al., 2020). Concessions are granted for various purposes, including agriculture, forestry, mining, infrastructure development, conservation, tourism, and industrial activities. The terms and conditions of a concession are typically defined through a legal agreement between the concession holder and the granting authority, specifying the rights, obligations, and limitations of both parties. This thesis primarily focuses on investigating the biophysical

outcomes of operational land acquisitions contained in the "Lao National Land Concession Inventory" (see Hett et al. 2020). Failed or unrealized land deals, which constitute a significant portion of total land deals, are omitted here and have received limited attention in existing research (Borras et al., 2022; Schönweger and Messerli, 2015). This is not trivial considering that many impacts of **land grabs** take place whether land deals materialize or not. Land grabs are defined "[...]among others as concessions or acquisitions of land that violate human rights and that are not based on transparent contracts or thorough assessments of social, economic, and environmental impacts" (Schönweger and Messerli, 2015, p. 94). The concept of "**green grabbing**" explains the appropriation of resources for environmental goals, often leading to adverse consequences for local communities (Fairhead et al., 2012; Scheidel and Gingrich, 2020). It emphasizes the connection between land cover, such as forests, and certain actors who anticipate advantages from its preservation, while excluding others like customary land users. Forest restoration initiatives, including REDD+ projects, can exacerbate existing inequalities by favoring political elites while marginalizing other social groups and their access to local resources (Scheidel and Gingrich, 2020).

All investigated topics of this thesis can be located within the realm of **sustainable development**. Sustainable development refers to a holistic approach to societal progress that aims to meet the needs of the present generations without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (WCED, 1987). It emphasizes the need to address social inequalities and improving human well-being without overshooting the world's ecological limits (Raworth, 2012). Sustainable development is often guided by frameworks, such as the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which provide a comprehensive set of targets and indicators to address various aspects of sustainability (UN, 2022). In this thesis, I examine the (sustainable) development objectives pursued by the Lao government, their underlying justifications, and certain ecological and food related trade-offs of associated LUCs.

3. Research questions

In my PhD research, I investigate the central question: How does Laos address the issue of land competition within the nexus between climate change mitigation and socio-economic development, and what are the resulting consequences? To this end, I analyze the nexus between climate change mitigation and development in Laos from two perspectives: i) the political intentions, and ii) the biophysical outcomes of land-use strategies observed in practice. The following detailed research questions guide this dissertation:

- I. What have been the discursive dimensions of sparing land and reducing shifting cultivation in policy documents?
- II. How have biophysical processes typically associated with land sparing affected greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in Laos?
- III. What (un-)intended consequences have emerged due to observed LUCs?

IV. What is the role of concession development in the overall climate impact of Laos's land use?

1. Research gaps

While addressing these questions, I intend to illuminate often overlooked phenomena in research and policy. Firstly, I aim to highlight the agricultural emissions associated with land-use intensification which are often disregarded in the literature, where the primary focus tends to be on livelihood and environmental changes, and in policies that prioritize economic aspects. Land-use intensification often involves industrialization processes and an increased reliance on fossil fuels, and thereby offsets the emission reductions achieved through forest conservation efforts (Gingrich et al., 2019). Secondly, I seek to emphasize the limited attention given to carbon fluxes in the land-sparing/land-sharing debate, where the focus is primarily on biodiversity and social aspects (Mertz and Mertens, 2017). Furthermore, Chapter 2 presents the first study examining the climate impacts of agriculture, tree, and mining land acquisitions at a national level in Laos. Previous investigations of large-scale land acquisitions have tended to focus either on global or local scales, resulting in either broad or very specific insights. By working at an intermediate scale, the nation-state of Laos, this research fills a crucial gap (Heinimann and Messerli, 2013).

Table 1 gives an overview about the main research gaps identified, the main research questions posed, my inherent research objectives, and the respective publications in which I have addressed them.

Table 1: Aims and objectives of the research conducted in this thesis.

RESEARCH GAP	RESEARCH QUESTION	RESEARCH OBJECTIVES	OUTCOME
(Hidden) Emissions from land-use intensification as well as implications for food security often remain neglected in research and policies.	What have been the discursive dimensions of sparing land and reducing shifting cultivation in policy documents?	Identification of major narratives.	Chapter 1: Bauernschuster, Pichler, Ingalls, et al. 2022
	How have biophysical processes typically associated with land sparing affected GHG emissions in Laos?	Verification or falsification of the occurrence of land sparing in Laos.	
	What (un-)intended consequences have emerged due to observed LUCs?	Linking observed LUCs with inherent GHG emissions or sinks, as well as with	

		emissions emerging from agriculture, and with agricultural production and food security indicators.	
Climate impacts of land acquisitions have not been analyzed at a national level in Laos yet.	What is the role of concession development in the overall climate impact of Laos's land-use?	Comparison of GHG emissions and sinks from concession development to GHG emissions and sinks from national LUC.	Chapter 2: Bauernschuster, Pichler, Nanthavong, et al. 2022

At the core of both chapters lie the themes of climate change mitigation and development. To explore the concept of "development", I employ diverse proxies that encompass food security and agricultural production as measurable biophysical indicators, and land-use intensification within the analyzed policies discussed in Chapter 1. In Chapter 2, the focus shifts to land acquisitions as a representation of development. Climate change mitigation is operationalized through the examination of GHG emissions and sinks, encompassing both nation-wide LUC and agricultural emissions in Chapter 1, and LUC associated with land acquisitions in Chapter 2. For a comprehensive overview, see Table 2.

Table 2: Proxies for development and climate change mitigation and scale of analysis in the chapters of this thesis.

Chapter	Development	Climate Change Mitigation	Scale of analysis
1	In policies: land-use intensification In analysis: food security, agricultural productivity	Carbon fluxes related to LUCs; Agricultural emissions	Nation-wide
2	Land acquisitions	Carbon fluxes related to LUCs	Within operational land deals

2. Innovative approach

The main innovative contribution of my thesis lies in its interdisciplinary approach, integrating qualitative and quantitative research methods. By combining discursive analysis of policy documents with quantitative analysis of carbon accounting, food security indicators, and agricultural production trends, the thesis provides a comprehensive understanding of the

complex interactions between social-ecological systems and political-ecological dynamics (Gottschlich et al., 2022). This integration allows for a more holistic assessment of LUC and its impacts. Moreover, the thesis extends beyond conventional assessments of land-use intensification by incorporating carbon fluxes as a crucial parameter. This expansion of focus beyond biodiversity and social considerations, commonly addressed in the literature, adds valuable insights to the field. Additionally, the thesis contributes to the discourse on justice in land concessions, which is often dominated by qualitative social science perspectives. By incorporating an ecological perspective, the thesis supports the need for more robust and comprehensive assessments of concession locations. Furthermore, the thesis offers meso-scale insights into land acquisitions, filling a critical gap as these analyses are typically conducted at either a global or local scale and tend to focus on one or two specific crops, with mining often being underresearched.

Overall, the integration of qualitative and quantitative methods, consideration of carbon fluxes, inclusion of an ecological perspective in justice analyses, and provision of meso-scale insights contribute to the novelty and significance of this thesis.

3. My work within HEFT

My research is embedded within the project Hidden Emissions of Forest Transitions (HEFT) led by Simone Gingrich and funded by the European Research Council (ERC)(heft.boku.ac.at). HEFT aims to systematically analyze socio-metabolic processes that facilitate forest regrowth, such as fuelwood substitution and agricultural intensification, and quantify the associated "hidden" GHG emissions and sinks (Gingrich et al., 2019). The project examines forest transitions in various contexts at local, national, supranational, and global scales, covering 19th-century Europe and North America, and 20th/21st-century Southeast Asia.

My research contributes to the study of GHG fluxes related to land-use intensification, particularly in the case study of Laos, Southeast Asia. Unlike the other case studies in the project, Laos did not undergo a forest transition, prompting me to analyze the actual biophysical processes taking place in the country. While my colleagues have primarily developed models (see for example Le Noë et al. 2020) or analyzed historical trends of forest carbon dynamics related to socio-metabolic processes *reducing* pressures on forests (see for example Gingrich et al. 2022; Magerl et al. 2019), my research centers on analyzing GHG emissions emerging from *increased* pressure on forests and agricultural activities in the recent past. A distinctive feature of my work within the project is the adoption of a PE perspective, with which I investigate the political narratives, interests, and actors that influence and are influenced by LUC in Laos. Another special aspect of my work is the focus on land acquisitions.

4. Chapters of this dissertation

Chapter 1: Discursive and biophysical dimensions of land sparing policies in Laos: Implications for greenhouse gas emissions and food security

Authors: Sonja Bauernschuster, Melanie Pichler, Micah Ingalls, Sithong Thongmanivong, Simone Gingrich

Journal: Published in *Land Use Policy*, Volume 120 in September 2022

Keywords: Land sparing; Shifting cultivation; Trade-off between environmental and development policies; Forest carbon sequestration; Agricultural intensification; Jevons' paradox

Chapter 1 provides two research foci regarding land use in Laos: first, we establish the policy context of land sparing in Laos. Second, we examine biophysical dimensions implicit in land-use policies such as de facto LUC, associated GHG emissions and sinks, agricultural production, and certain aspects of food security between 2000 and 2020.

Major derived narratives that are used in land-use policies since the 1980s circle around socio-economic and environmental arguments to legitimize goals like land sparing and the reduction of shifting cultivation. It is explicitly (in the environmental narrative) and implicitly (in the socio-economic narrative) assumed that land-use intensification enables forest regrowth and increases ecosystem carbon sequestration while improving food security. The biophysical trends, however, raise doubts concerning even the most basic assumption of the land-sparing argument: Lao land-use trends show that agricultural intensification in fact did not result in land being spared for conservation. Instead, cropland expanded into formerly forested or regenerating land, resulting in GHG emissions from intensified and expanded agriculture that are as high as those from shifting cultivation. Agricultural intensification reduced but could not eradicate food insecurity.

Contributions: I am the first author of the chapter and collaborated closely with Simone Gingrich and Melanie Pichler throughout the whole research process. Through extended and frequent discussion sessions held in our office in Vienna, during our joint research trips to Laos in 2019 and early 2020, and via zoom in times of the COVID-19 pandemic, we devised a research design for the manuscript. Collaborating with these experienced researchers from diverse disciplines helped me to clarify and contextualize the research topics I was working on, gain a better understanding of my results in a broader context, and refine my arguments and framing of the narratives I intended to write.

The other co-authors of this study, Micah Ingalls and Sithong Thongmanivong, are affiliated with institutions in Laos, including the Lao office of the Centre for Development and Environment (CDE), University of Bern, and the National University of Laos. Both facilitated

on-site data collection and expert discussions in Laos. During my research fellowship at the Lao office of CDE, I had valuable opportunities to engage with my colleagues, who possess extensive knowledge and experience in land-use mapping, data quality, and topics related to land-use intensification and commercialization. Through in-depth discussions, I gained insights from their years of work and expertise in these areas. Additionally, I conducted interviews with state representatives from various ministries (e.g., the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry), as well as representatives from conservation NGOs, donor organizations and tree plantation companies. While these interviews informed my research, they were not systematically integrated into my study.

Assuming a leadership role in the writing process represented a novel and enriching experience that presented both challenges and opportunities for growth. As I oversaw the development of the manuscript, I developed skills in coordinating and synthesizing interdisciplinary inputs into a cohesive, socio-ecological language, establishing suitable system boundaries for the manuscript, and ultimately assuming full responsibility for the content of the paper.

Next to writing the main text, my contributions in the research process encompassed several tasks. I gathered data and adapted the IPCC guidelines on carbon stock-difference methods to establish carbon fluxes. I assessed carbon flows from above- and belowground vegetation, excluding soil, in relation to nation-wide LUCs, and compiled relevant data from FAOSTAT on agricultural production and food security. I also conducted a qualitative content analysis, and analyzed and visualized all qualitative and quantitative results. I presented preliminary results at the 11th International Sustainability Transition (IST) Conference 2020 (<http://ist2020.at/>), the Third Biennial Conference of the Political Ecology Network (POLLEN) (<https://pollen2020.wordpress.com/>), and at a Research Seminar at the Institute of Social Ecology in 2020, and incorporated valuable feedback into the manuscript. All co-authors collaborated in discussing the results, drawing conclusions, and reviewing the manuscript. Micah Ingalls provided valuable input on food security in the Discussion.

Due to the challenges posed by COVID-19, finding reviewers for the peer-review process proved to be difficult, resulting in an 11-month delay in receiving feedback from Land Use Policy. However, alongside with Simone Gingrich I addressed the required revisions and completed a second round of minor revisions. Consequently, the paper was accepted in July 2022.

Chapter 2: Carbon emissions from land acquisitions in Laos

Authors: Sonja Bauernschuster, Melanie Pichler, Vong Nanhthavong, Rasso Bernhard, Michael Epprecht, Simone Gingrich

Journal: published in *Ecology & Society* (27/3) in 2022; contributes to a special feature called "Land acquisitions, Well-being, and Environment"

Keywords: Climate impact; Concessions; Emissions of land use; Green growth; Tree plantations

Chapter 2 provides new insights into the climate impacts of land acquisitions. In this study, our focus shifts from a nationwide perspective to LUC related to concessions in Laos, along with associated carbon emissions or sinks. Results indicate that between 2001 and 2017, land conversions caused by agriculture, forestry, and mining concessions resulted in net carbon emissions which accounted for 34% of the total emissions from land conversions on only 12% of all land conversions. Moreover, the findings suggest that even tree plantations that are intended to act as carbon sinks caused net emissions, although these data are the least reliable.

Similar to the approach taken in Chapter 1, we compare biophysical patterns with narratives related to shifting cultivation and observe that the denunciation of shifting cultivation is unwarranted when its relatively low carbon emission intensity is considered in contrast to the high carbon emission intensity of concessions. The pursuit of sustainable development could involve implementing measures such as reducing land acquisitions (particularly mining activities) due to their high emissions intensity, or mitigating emissions and social tensions arising from granted concessions by adopting approaches such as allocating land with low carbon densities, endorsing plantations characterized by high carbon density, and involving local land users from the initial planning phases.

Contributions: As in Chapter 1, I served as the first author for this chapter as well and collaborated closely with Simone Gingrich and Melanie Pichler, reaping the same benefits and engaging in thought-provoking discussions as described earlier.

Once again, all of the other co-authors are based in Laos, and I had the opportunity to meet and collaborate with them during my research stays in Vientiane in 2019 and 2020. These colleagues are affiliated with the CDE and participated in the initial compilation of the primary data source for Chapter 2, which is the "Land leases and concessions in the Lao PDR" inventory (Hett et al., 2020), which enabled them to provide extensive expertise on concession development. These international and interdisciplinary research partnerships enhanced the quality of both chapters by incorporating diverse perspectives, experiences, and knowledge into the research process. The diversity of cultural backgrounds, experiences, and viewpoints led me to reflect on ideas and approaches that I may not have otherwise considered, while also highlighting my positionality as a junior researcher affiliated with an institute located in a high-income European country.

Next to conceptualizing and writing the main text, my contributions to the study included collecting and analyzing relevant data, visualizing and interpreting the main results, coordinating and communicating work steps with all co-authors, and presenting preliminary results at the International Multidisciplinary Workshop: Contested Society-Nature-Relations (<https://www.flumen.uni-jena.de/en/workshop-contested-society-nature-relations-forest->

related-emotions-practices-conflicts-in-times-of-societal-change-27-28-may-2021/), integrating relevant feedback into the manuscript. Together with Rasso Bernhard, I collected and processed data on LUC in Laos with a particular focus on concession development. I also adapted the IPCC methodology to establish GHG fluxes. As in Chapter 1, all co-authors collaborated in discussing the results, drawing conclusions, and reviewing the manuscripts. Notably, Melanie Pichler contributed valuable input to the subsection "From Turning Land into Capital to green growth", and Michael Epprecht and Vong Nanhthavong drafted a paragraph on uncertainties in the land-use dataset for the subsection "Methods – Data". The paper was accepted with minor revisions, which I addressed alongside Simone Gingrich during the review process. As I was on parental leave during the final submission of Chapter 2, Simone Gingrich acted as the corresponding author.

Due to a steep learning curve and the similarities in quantitative methodologies between Chapter 1 and 2, producing results for the latter required less time. The most time-consuming aspect was the comparison and selection of appropriate carbon stock values for relevant tree and agricultural plantations. The entire manuscript was written more efficiently compared to the first manuscript, which could be attributed to several factors. Firstly, there was a significant time gap between the dissertation exposé and working on the manuscript, allowing for the concept of the paper to be well-developed based on literature review, interviews, and discussions conducted for the first chapter. Additionally, the learning curve for manuscript writing was steep, enabling the establishment of coherent arguments and a clear narrative. Moreover, the second manuscript was less experimental and involved fewer diverse methodologies, making it more straightforward to write and therefore completed more quickly. Lastly, all co-authors had become accustomed to remote communication, and effective communication channels had been established.

5. Discussion

1. Summary

The primary objective of this thesis was to enhance our understanding of drivers and consequences of competing land uses in Laos, where the scarce resource of land is simultaneously sought after for socio-economic development and climate change mitigation. To address the question of how Laos addresses the issue of land competition within the nexus between climate change mitigation and socio-economic development, and which consequences emerge thereof, I conducted an analysis of GHG emissions related to LUC associated with intensified land use, which had the potential for sparing land (Chapter 1), as well as climate impacts of land-concession development (Chapter 2).

Utilizing a PE perspective, this study also examined the discursive dimensions of land sparing in Lao policy papers, revealing that the Lao government has prioritized intensified and commodified land uses over the traditional practice of shifting cultivation, with the aspiration

of achieving both socioeconomic *and* environmental benefits (Bauernschuster et al., 2022a). While efforts to stabilize shifting cultivation and allow for forest regeneration have resulted in gross carbon sequestration, and whereas increased agricultural productivity has enhanced dietary energy availability and boosted agricultural exports, the expansion and intensification of cropland have resulted in significantly high GHG emissions. Furthermore, the observed LUCs have failed to ensure access to food and resilient livelihoods for everyone.

Concession development, another development strategy, has been characterized by a high carbon emission intensity associated with LUC, accounting for approximately 25% of total GHG emissions in Laos as of 2017 (Friedlingstein et al., 2022). This challenges the claims of *green* development put forward by plantation investors and the Lao government. It is important to note that the majority of concession-related land-use emissions originate from mining activities, which are not aligned with green development objectives. However, even tree plantations have been found to result in net emissions and have proven to be detrimental to the climate (Bauernschuster et al., 2022b).

The findings of this thesis highlight the intricate interplay among competing ecosystem services, including food production, resource provision, and carbon sequestration in the context of sustainable development in Laos. Land-sparing efforts alone turn out to be insufficient in balancing commercial and subsistence land use and the conservation of pristine land, and must be complemented by land-sharing approaches or undergo fundamental reconsideration in order to alleviate the nexus between climate change mitigation and development.

2. Limitations and ways ahead

Every scientific endeavor requires an honest reflection on its limitations to ensure a complete understanding of the research. In this thesis, the primary limitations revolve around the carbon density values associated with specific land-use categories. One major challenge stemmed from the lack of precise information regarding the ages of trees in tree plantations and the **rotation periods of shifting cultivation systems**. Due to this constraint, we had to rely on average stand ages and assumptions of relatively short fallow lengths, which led to conservative findings. The challenge with shifting cultivation systems is not only the variation in rotation lengths, which significantly affects aboveground carbon stocks, as demonstrated by chronosequence studies (Bruun et al., 2018), but also the difficulty in distinguishing shifting cultivation fallows from forests. Regenerating vegetation and young mixed deciduous forests often appear as continuous phases of regeneration, and distinguishing between them using satellite imagery is technically challenging (DoF, 2018). Future research will greatly benefit from closer monitoring of shifting cultivation at a higher resolution, as exemplified in the recent study by Chen et al. (2023), which allows for a clear distinction between different stages of regenerating vegetation and secondary forests.

Improving data robustness would also involve acquiring additional information on the **rotation lengths of tree plantations**, as here, too, carbon density varies depending on the specific stand ages. Currently, our assumption is that all tree plantations, or more broadly, all concessions in the base years 2000, 2005, 2010, and 2015, remained operational until the final year of analysis (2017). However, it is important to acknowledge the possibility of concessions being abandoned when yields or extractions prove to be lower than expected, which is quite common in boom-bust cycles (Schönweger and Messerli, 2015; Castella et al., 2023). Conducting yearly tracking of LUC over an extended period would yield valuable insights into the rotation lengths of both, shifting cultivation systems and tree plantations. Additionally, it would shed light on the actual activities on concession sites during the contract period, as well as on concession sites that are no longer in use, in particular as the first long-term concession contracts approach expiration. This is especially relevant for mining sites with their significant land clearing impacts, the legal obligation for (forest) land users to undertake restoration and reforestation efforts following mining operations, as stipulated in the Forestry Law of 2007, and the intricate nature of land restoration after mining operations (GoL, 2007; Sheoran et al., 2010). Qualitative research could provide valuable insights into the utilization of abandoned concession areas by local households, shedding light on the duration for which these sites are inaccessible to local land users, the methods employed by land users to reclaim the land, and the strategies implemented to effectively utilize the land once again.

A notable limitation of this study is the **omission of soil organic carbon** in the analyses, primarily attributed to limited availability of data. Bruun et al. (2021) emphasized the significant role of soil organic carbon in shifting cultivation systems, where its stocks rival those observed in old-growth forests. Strikingly, the study also revealed an overlooked aspect in land-use policies: shifting cultivation systems with short fallows exhibit higher soil organic carbon stocks compared to systems with extensive rotation. This can be attributed to the substantial and frequent input of decomposing root biomass into the soil, which positively influences the accumulation of soil organic carbon under the practice of recurrent slashing and burning. The exclusion of soil organic carbon introduced a potential bias into our findings, compromising the accurate representation of shifting cultivation systems.

3. Academic implications

When I started the research for my PhD, I did so under the assumption of a forest transition in Laos. My initial goal was to identify and account for hidden emissions of forest transitions, referring to emissions resulting from industrialization processes that facilitate forest regeneration (Gingrich et al., 2019). Examples for such processes include the substitution of fuel wood with fossil fuels, the outsourcing of logging industries to other countries, and the implementation of high-yield, industrialized agriculture that enables land to be reclaimed for reforestation (ibid.). However, upon receipt of updated LUC data, it became evident that forests in Laos were still declining, prompting a shift in my focus towards incoherencies between governmental objectives (e.g., increasing forest cover to 70%) and actual biophysical and socio-economic realities.

I found that, while emissions associated with **deforestation** were recognized in governmental development strategies, the proposed measures to address deforestation and forest degradation were somewhat one-dimensional, primarily targeting shifting cultivators, disregarding large-scale and industrial actors (Bauernschuster et al., 2022a). Unlike the overemphasis on emissions related to shifting cultivation, **intensified agriculture** is a frequently overlooked source of emissions within Lao land-use strategies. Shifting cultivation primarily contributes emissions during land clearing, whereas intensified industrial agriculture generates emissions predominantly due to its heavy reliance on fossil fuels (for fuel, synthetic fertilizers, pesticides, herbicides, and irrigation systems), as well as intensive livestock farming (particularly methane emissions from enteric fermentations in ruminants and various manure-related emissions)(Krausmann, 2004). In the HEFT framework proposed by Gingrich et al. (2019), these emissions would be termed "hidden emissions" if intensified agriculture resulted in spared land for afforestation. However, the findings of both publications in my thesis demonstrate how intensified land use, such as continuously cultivated cropland or land allocated for concessions, encroached upon extensively used shifting cultivation fallows and natural forests, resulting in emissions from LUC. The cumulative emissions from both intensified agriculture and land clearing contribute significantly to the overall emissions of land use intensification.

These findings contribute to various scientific debates. They inform, for instance, the ongoing land **sharing/land sparing discourse**, corroborating at a national level the insights from Vongvisouk et al. (2016). Their study demonstrated that the transition from shifting cultivation practices to intensified agriculture in the northern Lao Hua Meuang District did not result in either land sparing or sharing. By emphasizing the relevance of often neglected emissions of intensified agriculture and provoking thought about hidden emissions related to afforestation, I aimed to advance the research on land sparing. The emissions linked to **afforestation** through tree plantations on a national scale were not insignificant, as my research has revealed. It is essential that these emissions and their cause - concession development in forests - are acknowledged and promptly addressed in future development strategies. Moreover, the integration of national-scale assessments of soil organic carbon in future research may reveal that tree plantations established on shifting cultivation fallows actually result in land-use change emissions, contradicting my present findings, which propose these plantations as carbon sinks. In that scenario, tree plantations could only contribute to climate change mitigation if implemented on agricultural land, which raises concerns about environmental injustice and green grabbing.

My research revealed that a substantial portion of concessions nationwide was established on lands previously utilized by shifting cultivators, resulting in the displacement of these land users and reducing their livelihood resilience. In case of tree plantations, this land grabbing was legitimized under the pretext of climate change mitigation. My research thus contributes to the **discourse on green grabbing**. The handling of the trade-off between local livelihood resilience and climate change mitigation in favor of tree plantation development is intricately

tied to the perception of shifting cultivation practices as unproductive. I embedded the quantitative core of my work in political-ecological considerations about major narratives and **problematization** of certain land uses underlying Lao development policies (Bacchi, 2009). Lao development strategies tended to overemphasize the negative ecological and socio-economic consequences associated with shifting cultivation, while neglecting the positive aspects of shifting cultivation systems, such as their capacity for storing high carbon stocks in soils or the presence of Non-Timber Forest Products (NTFPs) in fallow areas (Bruun et al., 2021; Ingalls and Roth, 2018). Conversely, the detrimental effects of large-scale land investments and intensified land use, such as the displacement of local land users and soil degradation, were acknowledged but seemingly accepted in silence, given the government's plans to open over 600,000 hectares of land for tree plantations (MAF, 2018; Pichler and Ingalls, 2021; World Bank, 2019). Moreover, the positive effects and environmental claims of tree plantations were excessively emphasized. This thesis critically challenges the problematization of shifting cultivation in development policies, unveils the misconceptions surrounding carbon sequestration in tree plantations, and provides insights into the underlying factors of land grabbing, particularly green grabbing, in Laos.

By establishing connections between land use and land users and exploring the impacts of LUCs on local communities, I have in my research broadened the systems approach that is commonly employed in the social-ecological colonization concept by placing a stronger emphasis on the **level of actors**. Land-use change, as opposed to land-cover change, is intrinsically linked to land users, whose land-use practices are either facilitated or constrained by political decisions or ecological transformations. These individuals encounter varying degrees of access to land, which can be either enabled or restricted, and they must navigate a range of consequences associated with altered provisioning or access to ecosystem services. The comprehensive perspective of my research allows for a deeper understanding of the implications of development policies on the ground and facilitates the identification of potential trade-offs and the development of more contextually appropriate and inclusive approaches to sustainable development.

The research conducted in this thesis extends the scope of traditional LSS by incorporating normative considerations into land-related decision-making and governance. Following calls to embrace **normativity in LSS**, this discussion section aims to explicitly articulate the normative values and assumptions underpinning my research (Nielsen et al., 2019). Inherent values embedded in my research encompass climate regulating ecosystem carbon sequestration, livelihood resilience, the right to food and food sovereignty, as well as just land rights. While a multitude of other values, such as biodiversity conservation or ecosystem preservation, fall beyond the scope of this study, their importance is duly recognized. The focus on food security arises from ethical considerations and the long-standing attention given to land-use competition between food production and other land uses. Moving forward, inter- and transdisciplinary collaboration is essential, encompassing a wide range of problems, values, and perspectives. Recognizing that wicked problems such as the nexus between

development and climate change mitigation cannot be resolved by a single optimal solution, I have little faith in land-sparing approaches that claim win-win outcomes and often overlook trade-offs. Consequently, I am inclined towards prioritizing land-sharing approaches as more integrative and complex, although it remains uncertain whether they indeed perform better in balancing trade-offs.

4. Political implications

In the realm of sustainable development research, the **United Nations 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development** serves as the central normative framework worldwide (Biermann et al., 2022). While the SDGs have primarily impacted discourses, shaping how actors perceive and communicate about sustainable development, their potential for guiding societal transformation remains expandable. Realizing the full potential of the Agenda necessitates further research into human-environment system dynamics, contextual changes, conflicts arising from competing development agendas, and the influence of power relations (Messerli et al., 2019). As Messerli et al. (2019) emphasize, expeditiously providing policymakers with relevant and applicable knowledge is crucial to foster coordinated efforts for sustainable development in the next decade. My research contributes modestly to this pursuit, as demonstrated in the following paragraphs.

Laos has aligned itself with the United Nations 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, and has, in a unique addition, included an 18th goal, "Lives safe from UXO," to address the impact of landmines (unexploded ordnances = UXOs) and enhance the efficiency of mine removal due to the heavy bombing during the Vietnam War (United Nations Lao PDR, 2018). In the following section I will outline how this thesis contributes to addressing at least three SDGs, specifically SDG 2 (Zero Hunger), SDG 13 (Climate Action), and SDG 15 (Life on Land).

SDG 2, Zero Hunger, aims to end hunger, achieve food security, improve nutrition, double agricultural productivity and incomes of small-scale food producers, and promote sustainable agriculture (UN General Assembly, 2015). It recognizes that access to safe, nutritious, and sufficient food is a fundamental human right and an essential prerequisite for overall well-being. This thesis addresses SDG 2 by investigating the influence of LUCs on food security in Laos. It explores the effects of land-sparing efforts and land-use intensification on food production, access to nutritious land resources, and rural livelihoods. The findings indicate that, despite notable improvements in food security in recent years, food insecurity is still looming in Laos. The impending climate crisis and its potential adverse impact on agricultural yields is likely to exacerbate the situation. The allocation of land previously used for agriculture, like shifting cultivation fallows, to concessionaires, has negative consequences for local communities, leading to displacement and restricted access to essential food-producing land (Kenney-Lazar, 2016). While certain communities might gain from land acquisitions under specific conditions, the adverse impacts outweigh the opportunities of such land deals (Nanhthavong et al., 2021). To secure long-term food security and foster sustainable agriculture, policymakers in Laos must prioritize equitable access for farmers to essential

resources, such as land, markets, technology, irrigation systems, education, knowledge-sharing platforms, networking opportunities, and capacity-building initiatives (Castella et al., 2022). Antonelli (2023) emphasizes the importance of local and indigenous knowledge in creating sustainable food systems, highlighting how food production systems developed by indigenous peoples and local communities have nourished rural areas for centuries. By contrast, the viability and sustainability of pursuing a path of industrialization and commercialization of land as seen in other countries striving to achieve zero hunger, raises concerns. While it might be necessary to resort to such approaches to address the challenge of feeding a global population expected to reach 10 billion during the 21st century (UN DESA, 2022), the effectiveness of these approaches in the context of Laos remains uncertain.

SDG 13, Climate Action, focuses on taking urgent and ambitious action to combat climate change and its impacts. It recognizes that climate change poses a significant threat to sustainable development and calls for global cooperation to mitigate GHG emissions, build resilience, and promote sustainable practices (UN General Assembly, 2015). This thesis contributes to addressing SDG 13 by analyzing emissions resulting from LUC, agriculture, and the development of concessions in Laos. It identifies opportunities for reducing emissions and enhancing carbon sequestration through more sustainable land management. Importantly, the thesis challenges the prevailing notion that certain "green" actions, like tree plantations, are inherently climate-friendly, emphasizing the critical role of appropriate location selection (Bauernschuster et al., 2022b). It also challenges the prevailing "degradation narrative" that claims that shifting cultivation is the primary cause of degradation and should be eradicated as the primary target for climate action (Hajdu and Fischer, 2017). Instead, the thesis highlights the imperative for the Lao government to address alternative drivers of deforestation and degradation, such as mining concessions and the conversion of forests to cropland or tree plantations, along with emissions arising from industrialized agriculture, to make progress towards achieving SDG 13.

SDG 15, Life on Land, aims to protect, restore, and sustainably manage terrestrial ecosystems, halt biodiversity loss, and promote the sustainable use of land resources. It recognizes the vital role that healthy ecosystems play in supporting human well-being, biodiversity conservation, and sustainable development (Smith et al., 2019; UN General Assembly, 2015). This thesis addresses SDG 15 by assessing the ecological consequences of LUC in Laos. It identifies Lao strategies which try to integrate conservation and land-use practices to preserve ecosystems, protect endangered species, and maintain ecosystem services crucial for human well-being. The thesis highlights that the promoted land-sparing approach lacks the expected win-win outcomes of environmental and developmental gains due to intensified land use encroaching into forests and resulting in additional emissions, alongside those from intensive agriculture. To make significant progress towards achieving SDG 15, a comprehensive and integrated approach is essential, considering the interconnectedness between land use (and users), conservation, and sustainable development.

Throughout the discussion, **agroecology** has emerged as a promising approach to address land-use competition and sustainability trade-offs. The FAO defines agroecology as a holistic and integrated science, practice, and social movement applied in sustainable agriculture and food systems (FAO, n.d.). It offers site-specific solutions, incorporating local knowledge, ecological, social, and cultural contexts, supporting equitable and sustainable food systems aligned with the SDGs (Bruun et al., 2017; FAO, n.d.). To achieve transformative goals, the "Scaling up Agroecology Initiative" and the SDGs require a pluralistic approach. This entails maintaining diverse actor networks with varied structures and governance that foster innovation and are resilient in a changing environment (FAO, n.d.; Castella et al., 2022). Bottom-up and territorial processes are utilized to deliver agroecological solutions with a focus on people's needs. A study by Pichler and Ingalls (2021) highlights a **livelihood-based** development project in Laos, employing bottom-up and localized strategies, including participatory land-use planning and decentralized commercialization of agrobiodiversity. As the project faced challenges in aligning with the state's objectives of directing forest revenues into state bureaucracies, the broader integration of the livelihood project remained limited compared to extractivist or green development projects (ibid.). Lao policy makers could draw on this existing program and facilitate agroecological networks by providing support to multiple groups of actors. Both bounding within networks and bridging between networks are vital components of scaling agroecology innovations (Castella et al., 2022).

Other Southeast Asian countries face similar challenges as Laos. The insights gained from my research can be applied to scientific and political discourses around ecologically and socially sustainable land-use planning throughout Southeast Asia, where **deforestation** persists (apart from Laos in Cambodia, Indonesia, and Myanmar (FAO, 2020)), where various forms of **food insecurity** are looming (apart from Laos in Indonesia, Cambodia, Myanmar, the Philippines, and Timor-Leste (WFP, 2023a, 2023b, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e)), where **agriculture** plays a large role in rural livelihoods (apart from Laos in Myanmar, Cambodia, and Vietnam (Boughton et al., 2021; Ingalls and Diepart, 2018)), especially when **shifting cultivation** is practiced (apart from Laos in Myanmar, Indonesia, the Philippines, Vietnam and Thailand (Dressler et al., 2021; Eilenberg, 2022; Ingalls and Diepart, 2018; Pham Thu et al., 2020)) and criminalized, and where governments try to overcome socio-economic and environmental problems by applying **land-sparing** approaches (apart from Laos in Indonesia and Vietnam (Mertz and Mertens, 2017)) or by promoting **large-scale land acquisitions** (apart from Laos in Indonesia, Cambodia, Myanmar, the Philippines and Vietnam (Ingalls and Diepart, 2018; Nolte et al., 2016)) and other forms of large-scale commercial agriculture (palm trees/rubber plantations in Indonesia, Thailand, Malaysia, Cambodia, and Vietnam (FAO, 2020; Guillaume et al., 2018)). I advocate for closer cooperation between these countries to exchange knowledge and approaches they adopted to similar experiences regarding large-scale land acquisitions, consequences of land-use intensification, boom-bust cycles, conflicts over natural resources, and conservation efforts in their respective countries. Following my results, land-use planners in Southeast Asia should include a broader range of approaches apart from land sparing to meet development

and climate change mitigation (and adaptation) challenges. Careful considerations of locations for land deals (Is the predestined land actually degraded? Who uses the land currently? How can locals participate in location choices for land deals?) and other agreement specifics (How does the investor plan to use the land – is this ecologically and socially acceptable? Are there options for shared land use? What are appropriate compensations for people and nature?) are key to sustainable and just development, next to acknowledging that shifting cultivation – a practice which will probably remain part of rural livelihoods – is less harmful than often anticipated, and that land-use intensification seldom leads to land sparing.

6. Final remarks

The climate crisis as origin of a multitude of pressing challenges that disproportionately impact countries of the Global South requires a comprehensive array of measures. While afforestation alone is insufficient to mitigate escalating GHG emissions and needs to be complemented by other natural, societal, and technical solutions, it is imperative that afforestation efforts are implemented effectively to genuinely contribute to climate change mitigation rather than providing a false sense of security that hinders the adoption of more appropriate land uses and additional measures. Preserving tropical rainforests, in particular, is paramount to avert irreversible tipping points, and swift action is essential as the window of opportunity is rapidly closing, carrying dire implications.

Trade-offs are unavoidable, but - based on my norms and research derived beliefs – I argue that the fundamental human right of food security coupled with climate and environmental protection should be prioritized over the profit-seeking interests of a few.

In this context, it is crucial for policymakers to make well-informed, evidence-based decisions that prioritize the well-being of both humans and the environment, abandoning outdated narratives that misidentify shifting cultivation as the sole culprit for environmental degradation and associated GHG emissions. Instead, it is essential to recognize the significant role played by the expansion of intensive agriculture and the development of concessions in driving LUCs, which have far-reaching implications for climate change mitigation. By acknowledging these realities and adopting a holistic approach to land-use planning and policy formulation, policymakers can steer towards more sustainable and climate-resilient development pathways, ensuring the well-being of both present and future generations.

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Discursive and biophysical dimensions of land sparing policies in Laos: Implications for greenhouse gas emissions and food security

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ABSTRACT

Land-use competition between forest conservation and agricultural food production poses major threats to climate change mitigation and food security. Land sparing policies aim at reconciling this conundrum by intensifying agriculture while conserving forests, but scientific debates prevail about their effectiveness. To contribute to this debate, we analyze the discursive dimension of land sparing efforts and their biophysical implications for Lao PDR. Applying an interdisciplinary mixed-methods approach, we examine how Lao land-use policies legitimize land sparing at the cost of shifting cultivation and how land use changed between 2000 and 2019. We quantify ecosystem carbon fluxes and agricultural emissions and investigate trends in agricultural production and food security. We find that policy documents use both socio-economic and environmental arguments to substantiate land sparing at the expense of shifting cultivation. In biophysical terms, the stabilization of shifting cultivation enhanced the recovery of some forest areas resulting in gross carbon sequestration while ecosystems in total remained a net source of emissions. Concomitant agricultural intensification improved dietary energy supply, reduced the prevalence of undernourishment, and increased agricultural exports. However, cropland expansion and the intensification of agriculture entailed greenhouse gas emissions of similar extent as the continuing shifting cultivation, and could not prevent the prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the total population until today. We conclude that the narrow focus of land-use policies on land sparing falls short in effectively balancing societal needs and ecosystem functions.

1. Introduction

Land-use competition constitutes one of the fundamental trade-offs between environment and development policies in the Global South (Mertz and Mertens, 2017). Rising demand for land-based resources by domestic and foreign investors for commercial agriculture, mining and forest conservation increases pressure on land and traditional land users (Brogaard et al., 2017b; Haberl et al., 2014). Land-use policies have to navigate trade-offs between competing interests across temporal and spatial scales, considering, for example, the agricultural land needed to ensure food security while conserving land for carbon sequestration and biodiversity conservation (Messerli et al., 2015a).

Research distinguishes two possible directions in dealing with land-use competition: land sparing and land sharing (Mertz and Mertens, 2017). Land sparing assumes that clearly separated intensive agriculture

and forest conservation are best suited for reconciling development and environmental goals (Gibson et al., 2011; Phalan et al., 2011). The Borlaug hypothesis, for example, specifies that improvements in agricultural technology and ensuing higher yields result in land being spared for nature (Phalan, 2018). Land sharing, on the other hand, claims environmental and agricultural benefits from mosaic landscapes are more likely to preserve biodiversity in the long term, integrating low-intensity agriculture and managed forests along a continuum from field to fallow to forest (Perfecto and Vandermeer, 2010; Rerkasem et al., 2009a). While the scientific debate acknowledges the context-specific benefits and drawbacks of both approaches (Fischer et al., 2014; Law and Wilson, 2015; Meli et al., 2019; Phalan, 2018), in practice, policies often prioritize land sparing as a preferred alternative (Castella et al., 2013; Mertz and Mertens, 2017; Padoch and Sunderland, 2013). Often, this is formalized in national programs for Reduced

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Emissions from Deforestation and forest Degradation (REDD+) under the aegis of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC).

In Lao PDR (Laos), these divergent paradigms coexist, while proponents of each struggle for legitimacy as discourses crystallize into policies and practices under REDD+ and green economy directives (Pichler and Ingalls, 2021). At the crux of this issue lies the precarious present and uncertain future of traditional land-sharing shifting cultivation systems and largely state-driven initiatives to promote land sparing through agricultural intensification and enhanced forest conservation, a putatively more rational use of land (GoL, 2005; Ingalls et al., 2018). Laos aims at improving livelihoods, reducing poverty and graduating from its least developed status by the year 2024 (Souksavanh and Lipes, 2018), largely by tapping its terrestrial resources. Forests feature prominently in both socio-economic development and environmental protection programs with the overarching goal of reaching 70% forest cover (Phimmavong et al., 2009). The dual focus of the land sparing paradigm on forest protection and socio-economic development is especially appealing to a country like Laos with high levels of poverty and a self-declared dependence on the exploitation of natural resources for economic development (GoL, 2005; Lestrelin et al., 2012; Vongvisouk et al., 2016).

While land sparing synergies are framed explicitly in Lao land-use policies, inherent trade-offs remain largely implicit. Nevertheless, numerous studies have analyzed such trade-offs regarding biodiversity (see Mertz and Mertens (2017) for an overview) or challenged the basic assumption that intensified agriculture leads to spared land and might instead lead to an expansion of agricultural land (Ceddia et al., 2014; Lambin and Meyfroidt, 2011; Rudel et al., 2009), a phenomenon more generally described as Jevon's paradox (Phalan, 2018). Research increasingly addresses synergies and trade-offs with regard to carbon sequestration, as land sparing in theory leads to reforestation, considered one of the most important nature-based solutions for climate change (Hertel, 2012; Griscom et al., 2017). A number of studies compare carbon sequestration in spared forests and intensified cropland (e.g. Bruun et al., 2009; Gilroy et al., 2014; Lamb et al., 2016; Williams et al., 2018), and highlight greenhouse gas emissions associated with land-use intensification and agricultural industrialization such as the increased direct or indirect (e.g. in fertilizers) use of fossil fuels (e.g. Burney et al., 2010; Gingrich et al., 2019; Lamb et al., 2016).

Land sparing is also seen as an environmentally sound solution to meet rising food demand (Phalan et al., 2011), entailing land-use intensification and often commercialization, a process that often affects poor people's access to local food systems as forests, fallows, and agricultural fields are converted into more intensive agriculture (Broegaard et al., 2017a). This land-use change raises concerns about food security and resilience to price fluctuations, among others, as farmers abandon food crop production in favor of cash crops (Castella et al., 2013; Thanichanon et al., 2018).

Employing a social-ecological lens, this paper investigates land sparing strategies of Laos in terms of their environmental and socio-economic impacts in the period from 2000 to 2019. To this end, we (1) examine the discursive dimension of sparing land and reducing shifting cultivation in policy documents, identifying and characterizing major narratives; and (2) analyze biophysical processes associated with land sparing, focusing on (2a) land-use change, (2b) ecosystem carbon fluxes and agricultural emissions, and (2c) agricultural intensification and food security.

2. Methods

2.1. Discursive analysis of policy documents

The government of Laos (GoL) has identified the stabilization and reduction of shifting cultivation as a major political goal. It is formulated, for example, in the Lao Forestry Strategy to the Year 2020 (GoL,

2005), the National Socio-Economic Development Plans (NSEDPs) (GoL, 2016, 2006), the National Growth and Poverty Eradication Strategy (GoL, 2004) and is advanced as a cornerstone in Laos' Intended Nationally Determined Contribution (INDC) to climate change mitigation (GoL, 2015) and REDD+ documents (GoL, 2018, 2010). The Forestry Strategy explicitly summarizes Lao land-use policies since the 1980s and describes, among others, the environmental arguments in favor of reducing shifting cultivation. The National Socio-Economic Development Plans (NSEDPs) represent Lao economic development policies and highlight the economic benefits in terms of poverty reduction and food security associated with land sparing.

To analyze the discursive dimension of land sparing, we build on Mayring (2014) and conduct a qualitative content analysis focusing particularly on the Forestry Strategy 2020 (GoL, 2005) and the 6th and 8th NSEDPs (GoL, 2016, 2006), which are available online and in English. We use the coding software Atlas.ti to systemize and code targets, arguments and planned measures associated with reducing shifting cultivation in the three strategy papers. We choose the 6th and the 8th NSEDPs covering the years 2006–2010 and 2016–2020 in order to cover the timespan comprised by the Forestry Strategy as well as to detect changes in focus and rationale. Additionally, we qualitatively review Laos' REDD+ Readiness Preparation Plan of 2010 (GoL, 2010), first INDC report (GoL, 2015) and Reference Emissions-level report (DoF, 2018) in which the Lao government legitimizes the reduction of shifting cultivation in the context of carbon sequestration.

2.2. Biophysical assessment of land-use change

We use biophysical evidence to quantify changes in shifting cultivation in Laos since 2000 as well as specific ecological and economic impacts associated to land-use change.

2.2.1. Land-use change

To study changes in area extent and discuss land-use competition between conservation and production, we use national-level land-use change matrices between 2000 and 2019, focusing on changes in agricultural and forest lands: a decrease of shifting cultivation area would represent land-use segregation, i.e., a successful implementation of land sparing strategies. Data are provided online by the Lao Department of Forestry (DoF) and the Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA) for the periods 2000–2005, 2005–2010, 2010–2015, and 2015–2019 (<https://nfms.maf.gov.la/>).

Typically, land-cover assessments cannot detect the dynamic land-use system of shifting cultivation and no exact figures of one shifting cultivation land-cover category appear in land-use statistics (Heinimann et al., 2013). The classification used by the DoF allows distinguishing shifting cultivation area from forest and agricultural land, with "regenerating vegetation" and "upland crops" as the two land types considered to be mainly fallows and shifting cultivation plots. "Rice paddies", "agricultural plantations" and "other agricultural land" represent more intensively used, permanent agriculture, and "current forest" (in contrast to regenerating forest) is disaggregated into six ecological categories.

We use these data from national sources in our analyses because national decision makers use those data for land management plans and political strategies. However, we compare the national data to data compilations by FAOstat, providing much less information on shifting cultivation, but covering a longer time period (since 1990) and using a different forest definition. FAOstat data include forest areas with more than 10% canopy cover on 0.5 ha, while national data only report areas with more than 20% canopy cover on 0.5 ha as forests (DoF, 2018; FAO, 2012). Therefore, differences in values indirectly inform about forest quality. The land-use change matrices based on national data not only inform on a more detailed level about land-use changes, but are also the basis for accounting ecosystem carbon sequestration.

2.2.2. Ecosystem carbon fluxes and agricultural emissions

Changes in ecosystem carbon stocks and agricultural emissions are analyzed as proxies of climate impacts of land-use change in Laos in the period 2000–2019. We assess carbon stock changes in ecosystem biomass (excluding soil) through a stock-difference approach (IPCC, 2019, 2006) of six different forest categories, three agricultural land categories and two categories comprising shifting cultivation land. Carbon density values for 15 different land-cover categories are derived from DoF and IPCC (DoF, 2020, 2018; DoF and JICA, 2017; IPCC, 2003).

As we apply one value of carbon density for each land-use category, we can identify carbon fluxes due to conversion within forests, for example, from evergreen forests to plantations, or from evergreen forests to upland crops. We cannot, however, segregate different successional stages of shifting cultivation fallows, as we are not differentiating between young growth and old growth or between different ecological zones within Laos. Over- or underestimation of the carbon stored within this land-use category is likely, as is the overestimation of carbon stored in other forest categories where we cannot account for varying degrees of degradation (Gibbs et al., 2007; Hett et al., 2011). Bruun et al. (2018) and McNicol et al. (2015) have shown in Lao case studies that carbon stocks of fallows are systematically underestimated as the complex dynamics of root biomass and soil organic carbon in fallows remain poorly understood. In order to enable a better approximation of shifting cultivation-based carbon fluxes we compare respective national carbon stock values of regenerating vegetation with minimum and maximum values reported in the literature (Ziegler et al., 2012).

We complement the carbon stock-change estimation with an analysis of emissions from agricultural activities based on data provided by FAOstat (www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GT), computed at Tier 1 following the IPCC Guidelines for National GHG Inventories (IPCC, 2006, 2002, 2000, 1997, 1996). Results indicate to which extent emissions from land-use intensification compromise the forest carbon sink enabled by land-use segregation (Burney et al., 2010). Due to lack of data, our analysis is limited by i) excluding additional emissions from fossil-fuel based inputs (e.g. fertilizers, tractors) and from soils, ii) not discerning agricultural emissions intrinsic to different agricultural systems, and iii) not quantifying emissions per ton of (food and non-food) products of different cultivation systems.

2.2.3. Agricultural intensification and food security

To assess links between land-use change and food security in Laos, we use FAOstat to derive annual data on production, harvested area and trade of agricultural products, related to shifting cultivation (upland rice) and to commodified agriculture (maize, cassava, sugarcane, bananas, coffee) in the period 2000–2019 (<http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QC>). National statistics by the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, available since 2009, are used to corroborate aggregated FAO data. These provide more disaggregated data than FAOstat on the production of rice, the most important crop in Laos (Manivong and Cramb, 2020), that indicate subsistence farming (lowland rainfed rice), shifting cultivation (upland rainfed rice), and more commercialized farming systems (lowland irrigated rice), addressing impacts of agricultural system changes on rice production. We use population data provided by FAOstat (<https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/OA>).

Additionally, we analyze certain food security indicators. “Average dietary energy supply adequacy” operationalizes the physical availability of food which “addresses the ‘supply side’ of food security and is determined by the level of food production, stock levels and net trade” (FAO, 2008, p. 1). In addition, we investigate “prevalence of undernourishment” and “prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the total population” acknowledging that the mere supply of food does not guarantee household level food security. These indicators operationalize the physical access to food as presented as indicators for SDG target 2 “End Hunger” (<https://sdgs.un.org/goals/goal2>). All food (in-) security indicators are derived from FAOstat (<http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/FS>). While this selection is limited and not

representative of the actual food security of certain groups or individuals in the country, it captures biophysical variables (as opposed to monetary variables) that are associated with food security in the analyzed policy documents, and therefore allows for a review of the assumed relation between land sparing and food security.

3. Results

3.1. Environmental and socio-economic narratives to legitimize the reduction of shifting cultivation

Since the late 1980s, reducing shifting cultivation is a common goal in policies targeting socio-economic development and environmental protection in Laos (Castella et al., 2013; GoL, 2006, pp. 13; 176, 2005, pp. 39; 58). Based on the policy documents analyzed, we identified two narratives legitimizing this goal in the last 20 years (see Fig. 1): a socio-economic and an environmental narrative. Land sparing features prominently in both narratives, but is argued in different ways.

3.1.1. Socio-economic narrative: Reduction of shifting cultivation enhances food security and exports

The socio-economic narrative is based on the prevalent assumption that shifting cultivation is an “out-dated” (GoL, 2006, p. 176) form of agriculture. Therefore, “the areas of slash-and-burn rice cultivation should be reduced by introducing new livelihood alternatives, such as industrial tree plantations and commercial crops, livestock rearing, and other permanent livelihood alternatives” (GoL, 2006, p. 135). The Lao government prioritizes intensive, permanent and commercialized agriculture and forestry over shifting cultivation:

“The Government has concentrated on the development of agricultural production, to reorient the agriculture sector from semi-subsistence and subsistence to commercial production to ensure the enhanced supply of raw materials to the processing industries, meeting the growing domestic requirements for agricultural products, and rapidly expanding agricultural exports.” (GoL, 2006, p. 1).

Supply of fertilizers, pesticides, and improved, high yielding plant and livestock varieties, as well as implementation of irrigation systems and better infrastructure aims at upgrading farming methods (GoL, 2016, 2006). Concomitant yield increases as well as improved market access shall on the one hand improve people’s living standards, especially of subsistence farmers, by generating income, enhancing farmers’ job stability (GoL, 2016, p. 145), and leading to “firm food security” (GoL, 2006, p. 13). Especially the upgrading of rice production for domestic consumption and for reserves is expected to improve food security (GoL, 2016, p. 57, 2006, p. 135). On the other hand, cash crops like “corn, tobacco, coffee, beans, rubber, cassava, sugar cane, vegetables, and many types of fruit” (GoL, 2006, p. 65), high value trees (GoL, 2016, p. 107) and livestock (buffaloes, cattle) (GoL, 2016, p. 99) are promoted as export commodities. Increases of both domestic supply or food security improvements and export volumes imply an intensification of agriculture and the reduction of shifting cultivation.

Altogether, the “reorientation from shifting cultivation” to an intensified, commercialized agriculture should “gradually uplift the quality of life of the affected populations” (GoL, 2006, p. 34) and “reduce poverty among the ethnic people” (GoL, 2010, p. 10, 2006, p. 19).

3.1.2. Environmental narrative: Reduction of shifting cultivation supports forest conservation

Within the environmental narrative, shifting cultivation is framed as one of the main causes of deforestation and especially forest degradation (GoL, 2010, p. 30, 2005, p. 13), as “threats to forest and environment” (GoL, 2005, p. 42) and “one of the main causes of forest loss” (GoL, 2005, p. 42). “Alarming” rates of deforestation and forest degradation (GoL, 2005, p. 2) reinforce the goal to rehabilitate, preserve and expand forests to 70% of Laos’ total territory (GoL, 2005, p. 3). As one of the

Fig. 1. Narratives on socio-economic and environmental implications of land sparing or reducing shifting cultivation, derived from a qualitative analysis of policy documents in Laos.

main obstacles to increase forest cover, shifting cultivation shall thus be substituted by “rationalize[d] forest use” (GoL, 2005, p. 4). Large scale and industrial actors are acknowledged next to subsistence farmers as main drivers of deforestation and forest degradation (GoL, 2010). Derived measures, however, are mainly directed towards reducing shifting cultivation or illegal logging because they are “more directly under the control of the forest authorities” (GoL, 2018, 2010, p. 9; Skutsch and Turnhout, 2020).

The classification of different forest types as production, protection, conservation, regeneration and degraded forest (GoL, 2005, p. 11) supports the segregation between intensely and economically used forest areas on the one hand and spared, environmentally protected forest areas on the other hand. This stands in contrast to the shared land use of alternating shifting cultivation plots. Shifting cultivation fallows are classified as “degraded forest”, as “forests that have been heavily damaged, [...] that are classified for tree planting and/or allocation to individuals or organizations for tree planting, permanent agriculture and livestock production or other purposes in accordance with national economic development plans” (GoL, 2005, p. 11). The Forestry Strategy emphasizes that the categories of degraded and regeneration forest “make explicit intentions to regenerate natural forest by stabilizing

shifting cultivation and to productively utilize degraded forest land” (GoL, 2005, p. 11).

The environmental aims of forest conservation and reforestation shifted over the time period: Biodiversity conservation and stable wood supply have been prominent reasonings in the Forestry Strategy and the 6th NSEDP (GoL, 2006, p. 136, 2005, pp. 31; 51). Carbon sequestration and climate change mitigation in the context of international programs such as REDD+ became more important in recent years (GoL, 2016, p. 142, 2010, p. 48).

3.2. Land-use change, emissions and agricultural intensification

The identified narratives are based on the explicit or implicit assumptions that land-use intensification enables forest regrowth and increases ecosystem carbon sequestration, while increasing food security.

3.2.1. Land-use change

Since 2000, Lao forest area decreased according to both national and international data sources, albeit at different levels. National data show decreasing forest cover from 61% of the total land area in 2000 to 58% in 2019 (Fig. 2a), whereas FAO data (Fig. 2b) show decreasing forest

Fig. 2. Land-use change in Laos. National data present land-use change between 2000 and 2019 (a); Source: <https://nfms.maf.gov.la/>; FAO data present land-use change between 1990 and 2019 (b); Source: FAOstat.

cover from 71% in 2000 to 68% in 2019. The discrepancy in forest extent is due to different forest definitions in the two data sources. The difference in forest area might represent shifting cultivation fallow areas in early succession stages with canopy covers between 10% and 20%: the national dataset (Fig. 3a-d) shows that more upland crop plots are converted into regenerating vegetation (0.19/0.21/0.20/0.10 Mha/yr in 2000–2005/2005–2010/2010–2015/2015–2019) than the other way around (0.15/0.18/0.09/0.09 Mha/yr in the same periods), indicating aging fallows and a net abandonment or intensification of active shifting cultivation plots. Also, the FAOstat category “other land” is stagnating (16% in 2000, 17% in 2019). “Other land” is classifiable neither as forest nor as agricultural land, and thus can – like shifting cultivation areas – be both at the same time. Fallow areas seem to reach the threshold of 10% canopy cover, but not 20%, therefore those fallows are categorized as forests in the FAO data, and stagnate as “regenerating vegetation” in the national data (Fig. 2a, b). Due to the more inclusive forest definition in FAOstat, land-use changes or ecological succession processes are detected in this dataset rather quickly, but there is a risk of misinterpretations, e.g. of long-term fallows as “regenerated forest”. The DoF definition of “forest land” on the other hand has been adapted explicitly to avoid such misinterpretations by considering the typically

quick ecological succession in tropical and subtropical areas so that e.g. shifting cultivation fallows are not mistakenly classified as (sparse) forest (DoF, 2018). Still, the differentiation between “regenerating vegetation” and “mixed deciduous forest” remains challenging and possibly leads to an underestimation of the area extent of older fallows.

Both datasets show cropland expansions from 8% to 10% (FAO) and from 7 to 11% (national data) of total land between 2000 and 2019. Fig. 3a-c show that conversions into cropland (rice paddies and other agriculture (RP & OA)) mainly originate from former forests or regenerating vegetation. Conversions from forestland to upland crops do not occupy a large area, but were increasing from 2005 to 2015 (Fig. 3b-c), indicating that upland farmers still practiced pioneering shifting cultivation but at a small area extent. In the latest period from 2015 to 2019 (Fig. 3d), the share of forestland converted into upland crops decreased again, indicating a stabilization of pioneering shifting cultivation.

Our results thus show a slight decrease and then stabilization of shifting cultivation area with presumably increasing canopy density, while (primary) forests keep decreasing. Cropland expanded into both these land-use categories.

Fig. 3. Land conversions in the time periods 2000–2005 (a), 2005–2010 (b), 2010–2015 (c), and 2015–2019 (d). “RP & OA” stands for “Rice paddies and other agriculture”. Underlying data: <https://nfms.maf.gov.la/>, own representation.

3.2.2. Ecosystem carbon fluxes and agricultural emissions

Our assessment of ecosystem carbon stock changes reveals that land-use changes reduced ecosystem carbon stocks and caused net GHG emissions. GHG emissions increased from about 11 Mt CO₂-equivalents per year during 2000–2005 to about 15 Mt CO₂-equivalents per year from 2015 to 2019 (Fig. 4a). Analyzing the GHG effects of land-use changes in forests, agricultural land and shifting cultivation area, we see that the main emitting process was the conversion of forestland into shifting cultivation area, contributing 70% (2000–2005), 52% (2005–2010), 74% (2010–2015), and 62% (2015–2019) to gross land-use change related emissions (Fig. 4a). Conversions of forestland and shifting cultivation area into cropland also constitute emitting processes. Gross emissions of forestland to cropland conversions increased from 17% in 2000–2005 to 20% in 2015–2019. Gross emissions of conversions from shifting cultivation to cropland on the other hand decreased from 12% in 2000–2005 to 1% in 2015–2019, partly because such conversions occurred less, and partly because less fallows and more upland crop plots with reduced carbon stocks were converted. Converging carbon stocks in shifting cultivation areas and cropland result in less emissions in cases of conversion between those categories (DoF, 2020). Remaining land-use change related emissions were caused by conversions from forests to other land, and by conversions within forests.

GHG removals, i.e. carbon sinks, occurred mainly due to conversion of shifting cultivation area into forestland (54% of gross removals in 2000–2005, 83% in 2005–2015, and 87% in 2015–2019). Other land conversions additionally contributed to carbon sequestration at lesser extent, e.g. conversions within forests in 2000–2005, between shifting cultivation categories, or conversions from cropland to shifting cultivation area.

The magnitude of GHG emitting or removing processes depends on both the area extent and the respective carbon density values. Therefore, our results are sensitive to uncertainties in carbon density values. For the most contested carbon density value of regenerating vegetation, the DoF allocates rather low values (13.6 tC/ha) compared to the minimum (3 tC/ha) and maximum (138 tC/ha) values found in the literature (Ziegler et al., 2012), assuming short fallows (<7 years) and long fallows (>10 years), respectively. Allocating a carbon density value to regenerating vegetation at the lower spectrum of values from the literature seems appropriate considering that i) DoF only allocates fallows of max. 7

years to “regenerating vegetation” (older fallows are considered “mixed deciduous forest”), and ii) after a conversion from any other land use, fallows can be max. 4 years old: 1–2 year(s) active plot followed by 3–4 years fallow during the observed 5-year periods.

The low level of detail of our database does not allow to distinguish between old and young fallows, which is why we refer to the (young fallow) DoF values, risking potentially great underestimation of carbon stocks in (old growth) regenerating vegetation (Bruun et al., 2018; Chan et al., 2016).

Agricultural emissions represent 28–38% of the gross emissions from land conversion and agricultural activities (Fig. 4a). They increased between 2000 and 2019 from around 7 Mt CO₂-equivalents/yr to ca. 10 Mt CO₂-equivalents/yr, mainly due to livestock related emissions like enteric fermentation (52% increase) and emissions from manure management and applications (89% increase) (Fig. 4b).

While the conversion of forestland into shifting cultivation area was the main emitting process in 2010–2015 (54% of gross land conversion and agricultural activity emissions), the expansion and intensification of agriculture caused emissions of a similar extent, and in 2000–2005, 2005–2010, and 2015–2019, the conversion of shifting cultivation area and forest into cropland plus the emissions from agricultural intensification caused more emissions than conversions into shifting cultivation (55% compared to 45%, 49% compared to 38%, and 46% compared to 43% respectively). Our results thus on the one hand confirm that a reduction of shifting cultivation results in carbon sequestration in forest biomass. On the other hand, however, they also highlight that the expansion of agricultural land and the shift towards intensive agriculture results in emissions of an equal or even higher order of magnitude.

3.2.3. Agricultural intensification and food security

The DoF dataset indicates that the area of permanent agriculture has expanded faster than shifting cultivation area has decreased, meaning that overall, forest cover has decreased. Disaggregated, the DoF data show increasing areas of rice paddies (1.16 Mha/yr in 2000 to 1.2 Mha/yr in 2015), “other agriculture” (0.41 Mha/yr in 2000 to 1.05 Mha/yr in 2015; together with rice paddies 2.38 Mha/yr in 2019), and agricultural plantations (0.05 Mha/yr in 2000 to 0.08 Mha/yr in 2019), while upland crop areas decreased (0.19 Mha/yr in 2000 to 0.13 Mha/yr in 2019) (Fig. 5a). “Other agriculture” is increasing so steeply that it

Fig. 4. Ecosystem carbon fluxes and agricultural emissions. a) Emissions and Removals of GHGs (in CO₂ equivalents/yr) due to land conversions and agricultural activities. F/F: conversions inside forests; SC/F: conversion from shifting cultivation (SC) to forest; C/F: conversion from cropland to forest; F/SC: conversion from forest to SC; SC/SC: conversion of SC fallows and active plots; C/CS: conversion from cropland to SC; F/C: conversion from forest to cropland; SC/C: conversion from SC to cropland. C/C: conversions within cropland. Net other land: conversions of all categories into other land and from other land into all categories. The bar charts indicate minimum and maximum net emissions based on min./max. values from the literature compared to emissions based on DoF C density values of SC. b) Agricultural Emissions in Mt CO₂ equivalents/yr in Laos; Source: FAOstat.

Fig. 5. Agricultural intensification displayed by cropland conversions and production quantities. a) Conversions within cropland 2000–2019 in Mha; Source: DoF; b) Crop production in Mt dry matter per year; source: FAOstat; disaggregated rice production in Mt dry matter / year; source: Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry.

proportionally catches up with rice paddies in 2015, with maize, vegetables, cassava, and sugar cane as main contributors according to FAOstat. Rice, however, remains the most important crop regarding area and production output.

Crop production more than doubled between 2000 and 2019 from 2.3 Mt dry matter/yr to 5.2 Mt dry matter/yr with a peak in 2016 (6.6 Mt dry matter/yr), a much more rapid growth than that of the production area (1.6-fold), or that of population (1.3-fold) in the same period (Fig. 5b), indicating agricultural intensification and increasing per-capita production. “Cash crops” such as maize, cassava, sugar cane, and bananas contributed to the observed increase in production, partly due to expansion of cropland, partly due to increasing use of improved cultivars (Ingalls et al., 2018). Rice production also increased in absolute terms, but its share in total crop production declined from 82% in 2000 to 58% in 2019. Instead, the shares of maize, cassava and sugarcane increased from 4% to 13%, 1% to 12%, and 2% to 5% respectively between 2000 and 2019. Adverse weather conditions with severe floods and droughts as well as pest infestations led to steep declines in production quantities of rice (minus 15%) and maize (minus 49%) in 2018 and 2019 (FAO, 2020).

When looking at the more disaggregated national data on rice production, the category considered a shifting cultivation crop (“upland rainfed paddy”) decreased from c. 0.19 Mt dry matter/yr to 0.15 Mt dry matter/yr between 2009 and 2019, while the category considered a cash crop (“dry season paddy”) stagnated at around 0.4 Mt dry matter/yr (Fig. 5b). “Lowland rainfed paddy” however increased from around 2 Mt dry matter/yr in 2009 to c. 2.5 Mt/yr in 2019.

Laos is not a large importer or exporter of agricultural biomass, with gross trade flows accounting for less than 5% of agricultural production in the entire period since 2000. Nevertheless, trade experienced a steep rise since 2013 to up to 18% in 2017 due to increasing cassava (0.1 – 0.7 Mt of dry matter) and maize (0.10 – 0.16 Mt of dry matter) exports. Since 2008, Laos has been a net exporter of agricultural biomass products (Fig. 6a).

“Average dietary energy supply adequacy” exceeds 100% since 2004–2006, indicating a stable and sufficient national supply of nutritional energy (Fig. 6b). The prevalence of undernourishment decreased between 2000 and 2002 (31%) and between 2015 and 2017 (6%), and stagnated at a level of 5–6% until 2018–2020. No trend data of the prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the total population

Fig. 6. Agricultural trade and food security indicators. a) Physical trade balance of agricultural crops and livestock products; negative values indicate an export surplus, positive values indicate that more products are imported than exported; Source: FAOstat; b) Set of food security indicators: “Average dietary energy supply adequacy”, “Prevalence of undernourishment” and “Prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the total population”; Source: FAOstat.

is available, only one value of 29.4% in 2018–2020, showing that there is still roughly one third of the population suffering of moderate or severe food insecurity today.

While the shift in relative contribution to agricultural production from upland crops to lowland rice and cash crops increased Lao export volume and availability of food, food insecurity still affects a high share of the Lao population.

4. Discussion

Our results provide empirical grounds for a more nuanced and critical reflection of the land sparing assumptions in Lao policies that legitimize the reduction of shifting cultivation: On the one hand, the stabilization of shifting cultivation resulted in recovery of some forest areas entailing gross carbon sequestration, while agricultural intensification improved dietary energy availability and increased agricultural exports. On the other hand, however, cropland expansion and intensification of agriculture resulted in equally high GHG emissions, and were unable to guarantee access to food for everyone.

The results confirm Vongvisouk et al.'s (2016) observation that land-use change in Laos resulted in “neither land sparing nor land sharing” (p. 190), as permanent croplands instead of forests substitute the slightly decreasing shifting cultivation area. No land was spared, and despite the establishment of National Protected Areas and the overarching aim to achieve 70% forest cover by 2020 (GoL, 2005), forest cover decreased between 2000 and 2019. At the same time, agricultural land use intensified *and* expanded as would be expected according to Jevons' paradox: efficiency increases due to agricultural intensification were overcompensated by the expansion of cropland that was much greater than that needed to replace the production from shifting cultivation, possibly due to rising demands and increasing margins (Phalan, 2018). Shifting cultivators who abandoned former plots and fallows partly did so because laws and policies restricted access and use of land to either agriculture or forestry and criminalized shifting cultivation, and partly because of improved integration into markets and infrastructure (Fujita and Phanvilay, 2008; Van Vliet et al., 2012). The transition from shifting cultivation to market-oriented, high yielding agriculture potentially results in immediate economic benefits for farmers, reducing their dependency on subsistence production (Evans et al., 2011; Van Vliet et al., 2012), though this may be more pronounced for wealthier farmers who possess sufficient resources for transition (Hepp et al., 2019). This, in addition to the policies promoting agricultural commercialization and intensification, possibly encouraged farmers and investors to transform and expand their agricultural production, leaving no land to be spared for conservation (Rudel et al., 2009; Van Vliet et al., 2013, 2012).

A positive contribution to climate change mitigation through land sparing can only succeed if the reduction of shifting cultivation is met with forest protection and increased carbon sequestration (Burney et al., 2010). We found that conversions from forestland to shifting cultivation areas caused the highest land-use change related GHG emissions. Soil organic carbon of shifting cultivation plots, however, was not considered. According to recent and Lao-specific studies by Bruun et al. (2021) and McNicol et al. (2015), shifting cultivation fallows store much more carbon in soil and root biomass than is typically expected. Taking soil organic carbon and root biomass in fallows into account could therefore change the picture.

The actual extent of land-use change induced carbon emissions and removals can only be approximated, because biomass carbon densities in shifting cultivation systems are highly context-specific and data availability is poor. Biomass carbon density depends, among others, on the length of the fallows in shifting systems, and on forest characteristics (primary or planted forest, species of planted trees, etc.) (Fox et al., 2014). Hence, future benefits of promoted land-use changes (e.g. shifting cultivation to segregated agriculture/forest) in terms of carbon removals might be limited. The promotion of one unspecified land-use category against another with presumably less carbon sequestration

potential might be disproportionate, as the specifics of those categories can change the whole picture (Mertz et al., 2021) – long-fallow shifting systems for example may store as much carbon as intact forests, while short-fallow systems (Ziegler et al., 2012) may store less carbon than perennial plantations of e.g. rubber (Bruun et al., 2018), whereas systems of permanent cropping of continuous annual field crops (Ziegler et al., 2012) might store less carbon than even intensive shifting cultivation systems (Bruun et al., 2021).

In addition to the low carbon sequestration potential of permanent cropland, agricultural intensification itself is a source of growing GHG emissions that may compromise protected forest carbon sinks (Gingrich et al., 2019). Our results show that emissions related to intensive livestock farming and rice cultivation aggregate and, together with the emissions of land conversions into cropland, can reach the level of emissions produced by land conversions from forests into shifting cultivation area. The high GHG emissions from permanent agriculture (e.g. emissions from fertilizer production) as well as emissions associated to shorter fallow periods (e.g. emissions from soil degradation) are so far missing in narratives supporting the reduction of shifting cultivation and should be integrated in future policies for the benefit of more expedient land-based climate change mitigation measures (Scheidel, 2018).

While our results show that agricultural outputs increased in total, per hectare, and per capita, thus contributing to an improvement in the average national availability of food and a decrease of biomass import dependency, FAO data suggest that food security is still precarious. Undernourishment and moderate to severe food insecurity prevail until today at considerable levels. Land sparing policies assume that the mosaic landscapes of shifting cultivation are “underutilized” (Messerli et al., 2015b; Scheidel and Work, 2018) and neglect empirical evidence that small-scale agriculture adopting agroecological methods can be as productive as industrial agriculture, or even more productive (Perfecto and Vandermeer, 2010). This perception may have negative implications for climate change mitigation (if plantations or cropland with low carbon density substitute long-fallows) but also questions customary land use and ultimately endangers local people's food security (Keovilignavong and Suhardiman, 2020). Further, there is a large degree of uncertainty regarding the adequacy of food security indicators with respect to their ability to capture the overall diversity of plant and animal species used within complex systems (Armstrong, 2018; Barrett, 2010; Jones et al., 2013). Typically, comparative analyses of agricultural production between extensive (i.e. those based on land sharing) and intensive agricultural production systems, and their relationship to food security, include only the formal or dominant agricultural product. In rotational agriculture systems in Lao PDR and similar contexts this is typically rice. Artificially narrowing comparative analyses in this way excludes one of the key features of extensive upland systems, wherein ancillary crops and species — particularly non-timber forest products (NTFPs) — play a crucial role in overall production at the landscape level. While no national-level assessment of production and consumption levels of these species has been carried out, a growing body of literature sheds some light on this particular matter (e.g. Bouapao et al., 2016; Epprecht et al., 2018; Hett et al., 2012; Ingalls and Dwyer, 2016; Keovilignavong and Suhardiman, 2020; Renard and Tilman, 2019). NTFPs collected from shifting cultivation fields and their associated fallows in many areas comprise the principal source of the non-rice diet and, in some cases, exceed the value of rice sales in their proportional contribution to the household income (Ingalls and Roth, 2018). While land sparing advocates imply that forest conservation necessarily leads to overall increase in NTFPs (because of the supposed positive association between these and forests — the F in NTFP), this does not appear to be the case. Emergent data from a 10-year assessment of more than 3000 upland households in Lao PDR indicates rather that 48% of NTFP sale values derive from shifting cultivation fields and their fallows, versus only 10% from mature forest areas (Ingalls and Roth, 2018). Intensive agricultural systems, which are explicitly designed and managed to limit

species diversity within cropping regimes, are comparatively lacking in these values (Rerkasem et al., 2009b). The prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity is likely linked to the expansion of commercial agriculture that often leads to the specialization in a small number of cash crops (Thanichanon et al., 2018). This specialization leaves farmers vulnerable to extreme weather events and food price volatility and, at times, limits their ability to buy food (FAO, 2020; Thanichanon et al., 2018). Additionally, increasing the share of intensively produced food might (further) skew internal inequalities in food distribution. The commercialization of agriculture enhanced the well-being of many well-connected villages but it also exacerbated the threat of food insecurity for certain groups of the population less connected to distant markets (Castella and Phaipasith, 2021; Nanthavong et al., 2021). While shifting cultivation used to be a reliable food security practice for most, land degradation due to shortened fallows has led to poor harvests and an unstable food supply (Ramcilovic-Suominen and Kotilainen, 2020), as well as the degradation of underlying soils (Mertz et al., 2009; Vandergeest, 2003) and the robustness of fallow-based resources (Fox et al., 2014; Fujita and Phanvilay, 2008). Therefore, further marginalizing shifting cultivation has direct negative implications for food security of the most vulnerable rural populations in Lao PDR, by depriving them from the collection of NFTP which are a crucial additional source of food or income (Jendresen and Rasmussen, 2022; Ramcilovic-Suominen and Kotilainen, 2020; Vongvisouk et al., 2014). This deprivation has not been compensated by agricultural intensification on permanent croplands.

5. Concluding remarks

Our analysis combined qualitative and quantitative approaches to study the discursive and biophysical dimensions of land sparing strategies in Laos, focusing on a reduction of shifting cultivation. We highlight that while the reduction of shifting cultivation is politically considered a win-win solution to achieve economic and environmental aims, the biophysical trends in land-use change, GHG emissions and food security only partially support this perception because the shift to intensive commercial agriculture also negatively affects GHG emissions and was unable to eradicate food insecurity even in years with high production. Effective land-use policies need nuanced perspectives, addressing positive and negative implications of all agricultural and forest practices.

This begs the question of the degree to which interventions designed to avoid forest carbon emissions and enhance atmospheric carbon removals are able to produce these outcomes in practice. Our research suggests that where such interventions focus on land sparing approaches that transform (some part of) shifting cultivation systems to intensive agriculture, these outcomes are ambiguous at best. Beyond all this, the particular promise of REDD+ — to take one example of a global policy initiative wherein the carbon implications of competing land uses are explicitly addressed — is that it is intended as a tool not only to address forest carbon emissions (and thus climate change mitigation), but also to achieve ancillary positive outcomes for biodiversity and people. Insofar as REDD+ approaches and land-use policies in general are grounded in and share the assumptions of land sparing paradigms, we suggest that they will largely fail to achieve these. Creating political space for land sharing and carbon-cycle management through extensive systems, while also explicitly recognizing potential tradeoffs, may yet achieve a more realistic, negotiated ‘win-win’ for a more sustainable future.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at doi:10.1016/j.landusepol.2022.106293.

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Chapter 2: Bauernschuster, Pichler, Nanhthavong, et al. 2022

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Carbon emissions from land acquisitions in Laos

[Sonja Bauernschuster](#)¹

ABSTRACT. Large-scale land acquisitions repeatedly fall short of their acclaimed socioeconomic benefits and are associated with unintended social, economic, and ecological costs. In Laos, the government has started to question its own “Turning Land into Capital” policy, and reviews land acquisitions or concessions with regard to their socioeconomic impacts. Empirical investigations of environmental impacts of land concessions, however, remain underrepresented. We link the nation-wide concession development between 2001 and 2017 with associated land use changes and quantify related land use change-induced emissions. Results show that land acquisitions for agriculture, forestry, and mining affect mainly forests and land previously used for shifting cultivation and permanent agriculture; e.g., rice paddies. Consequently, land conversions caused by concessions resulted in net carbon emissions of 4.9 Mt CO₂e yr⁻¹ on average in 2001–2017, which amounted to 34% of total emissions from land conversions. Even tree plantations that are meant to serve as net carbon sinks caused net emissions, but those data are the least robust. The relatively low carbon emission intensity of shifting cultivation compared to the high carbon emission intensity of concessions challenges the dominant narrative of shifting cultivation as a causal factor for forest degradation. Political means of fostering sustainable development include the reduction of land acquisitions because of their emissions intensity, and minimization of emissions and social conflict induced by granted concessions, for example, by allocating land with low carbon densities and obtaining consent of local land users.

Key Words: *climate impact; concessions; emissions of land use; green growth; tree plantations*

INTRODUCTION

Since 2000, the scale and pace of the global land rush have been unprecedented (Liao et al. 2021), with particular ramifications on agrarian and environmental transformations in Southeast Asia (Corbera et al. 2017, Schoenberger et al. 2017, Ingalls et al. 2018). Laos is one example where investments from neighboring countries and beyond resulted in a “massive boom in large-scale land concessions”^[1] (Baird 2011:15) in agriculture, forestry, hydropower, and mining (Hett et al. 2020). Since 2000, the Government of Laos has granted concessionaires access to 4% of the domestic territory, expecting infrastructure development and government revenues in return (Hett et al. 2020). This policy of “Turning Land into Capital” (Baird 2011, Kenney-Lazar et al. 2018) aimed at closing yield gaps, increasing food and energy security, improving off-farm employment opportunities, and enhancing local and international market access for agricultural, timber, and mining products (GoL 2004, 2006). At the same time, land acquisitions for tree plantations and agricultural products were expected to increase the productivity of national land use, allowing for land sparing of so-called marginal land, and thus contributing to climate change mitigation (Baird 2011, Fairhead et al. 2012, Davis et al. 2015b, Liao et al. 2021). We investigate the impact of concession development on biomass carbon (C) emissions in Laos since 2000, including agricultural and tree plantations as well as mining concessions, and discuss policy implications in view of sustainable land use.

In Laos, a country endowed with vast natural resources, the commodification of land is considered an attractive opportunity for economic growth and poverty alleviation to escape least-development status (GoL 2006, Lu and Schönweger 2019). Recently, the Government of Laos has started to address environmental concerns in its development plans, which has given rise to green growth strategies, with tree plantation development and sustainable agricultural intensification as main pillars (GoL 2018). In order to efficiently use natural resources, modernize land

use practices, and combat poverty, the Government of Laos now preferably grants land concessions on land labeled as degraded land or potential forest (GoL 2007, Baird 2014, MRLG 2019). In the northern province of Luang Namtha, for example, tens of thousands of hectares of Chinese rubber plantations were approved as an instrument to replace shifting cultivation (and eradicate opium production) during the rubber boom decade of the 2000s (Shi 2008, Baird 2010). In the fertile Bolaven Plateau in the southern province of Champasak, in turn, large-scale coffee plantations, bauxite mining, and hydropower dams partially replaced the allegedly less efficient smallholder coffee farming (Delang et al. 2013).

Investors readily pick up the legitimization framework for “green grabs” (Fairhead et al. 2012:237) in the case of tree plantations (Scheidel and Work 2018, Liao et al. 2021), and are in general attracted by Laos’s allegedly “untapped resource frontier” (Barney 2009:147), low cost of land, and weak land governance (Baird 2010, Lu and Schönweger 2019). Concessions, however, have often fallen short of meeting both the government’s and investors’ expectations. Some have never materialized (Schönweger and Messerli 2015, Lu and Schönweger 2019, Baird 2020), while some compete with local people’s needs for arable land and other natural resources, thereby challenging local livelihoods and reinforcing trade-offs between food sovereignty, income, and livelihood resilience (Baird 2010, Nanththavong et al. 2020).

A considerable number of researchers have investigated socioeconomic impacts of land acquisitions in recent years (Hall 2013, Friis and Nielsen 2017, Malkamäki et al. 2018, Müller et al. 2021). Emerging evidence also links land acquisitions to environmental impacts such as deforestation (Davis et al. 2015a, 2020), soil degradation (Shete et al. 2016), pressure on the local water balance (Breu et al. 2016), and chemical pollution (Friis and Nielsen 2016). However, there is less research on climate-

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related impacts of the land rush (Liao et al. 2021). Liao et al. (2021) conducted the first study on global carbon (C) emissions related to land acquisitions for agricultural purposes, which showed negative climate effects but also potential savings if acquisitions occur only in areas with low carbon stocks. Furthermore, several case studies have quantified carbon stock (changes) in certain tree plantations in the tropics, and have suggested a range of carbon impacts can occur depending on plantation type, age, management, and vegetation prior to land conversion (e.g., Forrester et al. 2006, Du et al. 2015, Bruun et al. 2018, Guillaume et al. 2018). Less research on climate-related impacts of agricultural and mining concessions has been published (Hergoualc'h and Verchot 2011, Hergoualc'h et al. 2012, Bordonal et al. 2017). We contribute to this line of research by establishing the first nation-wide accounting of biomass carbon emissions caused by the implementation of land concessions in Laos, including tree plantations, agriculture, and mining.

Based on a recent inventory of land concessions in Laos and spatially explicit information on land cover, we assess all aboveground and belowground biomass carbon fluxes (emissions and sinks, excluding soil organic carbon) that have resulted from concession-related land use changes in Laos in 2001–2017. By comparing these carbon fluxes to national carbon fluxes from land use change, we are able to elucidate the role of concession development in the overall climate impact of Laos's land use. In addition, we identify which concession types are most critical and which previous land uses (and land users) are most affected by land acquisitions. We reflect on our results in view of their policy implications, aiming to stimulate a more nuanced discussion on concession granting and development in Laos and other countries, considering its effects on the global climate, as well as on local livelihoods.

From Turning Land into Capital to green growth

Compared to other Southeast Asian countries, land acquisitions in Laos have a relatively short history. Since the early 2000s, the Government of Laos has promoted land acquisitions through creating favorable conditions for Foreign Direct Investment in the course of the Turning Land into Capital policy (Kenney-Lazar et al. 2018:iv). Although the Government of Laos has never officially used the term in regulations or laws, in practice, the policy is aimed at commodifying natural resources, mainly for hydropower, infrastructure development, and mining, as well as agricultural and tree plantations, in return for state revenues and infrastructure and service provisioning (e.g., [rail]roads, health centers) (Ingalls et al. 2018:104, Kenney-Lazar et al. 2018).

The Lao Ministries of Natural Resources and Environment, Agriculture and Forestry, Planning and Investment, and Energy and Mines recently completed the most comprehensive inventory of land leases and concessions in Laos to date (Hett et al. 2020). An analysis of the inventory data shows that of the 1 million hectares of land that have been granted as concessions for development in the primary sector, more than half has been granted for agricultural (mainly sugarcane, cassava, cattle and buffalo, coffee, and jatropha) and industrial tree plantations (mainly rubber, eucalyptus, and agarwood), followed by 415,527 ha of land granted for mining concessions (mainly gold, copper, and potassium). Not all area granted has actually been developed

by the investors; however, when concessions were developed, they were often in primary (18%) or secondary forests (26%), but also in land that was previously used for shifting cultivation fallows (15%), gardens (9%), rice paddies (4%), grazing (4%) or upland agriculture (3%). Only 1% of concessions were allocated in degraded forest (Hett et al. 2020:67), where concessions initially were meant to be developed (GoL 2007). The neighboring countries of China, Vietnam, and Thailand are the most important investment and trading partners, each investing primarily (but not exclusively) in land concessions in geographic proximity.

Bolikhamxai and Vientiane in the center of the Laos are most affected by large amounts of land developed under both domestic and foreign concession agreements, where mostly mining concessions have been developed (Fig. 1); in Savannakhet and Champasak in the south, concessions were more evenly distributed among agriculture, tree plantations, and mining. In the north, Luang Namtha is almost exclusively affected by the development of tree plantations. Less affected regions can be found in remote areas (Messerli et al. 2015), such as Houaphan or Xiengkhoang.

Fig. 1. Most common concession types (pie charts) and concession occurrence (shades of blue) in all provinces in Laos based on data provided by the inventory of land leases and concessions in Laos (Hett et al. 2020).

Concession development has been a key driver of economic growth in Laos over the past 20 years (Nanhthavong et al. 2021). In the recent decade, however, mounting evidence of increasing land conflicts, declining commodity prices (especially for rubber), and low return on concessions investments due to lack of effective management structures in the Government of Laos led the government to announce several concession moratoria, starting in 2007 (Kenney-Lazar et al. 2018, Dwyer and Vongvisouk 2019, Hett et al. 2020). Most prominently, PM Decree No. 13/2012 suspended new concessions for rubber, eucalyptus, and mining exploration until the end of 2015, and was extended until 2020 (Hett et al. 2020). At the same time, the Government of Laos started to revise the Land Law of 2003 in an effort to move to quality investments. The amended Land Law of 2019 reduced the period of concessions from indefinite to 50 years (Art. 120) and implemented the compulsory approval by the National Assembly for concessions that exceed 10,000 ha (Art. 29.3) (National Assembly 2019). Furthermore, the law requires companies to survey and map out the actual land area before rather than after the concession is approved (Kenney-Lazar et al. 2018).

In the course of these adjustments, green growth strategies have increasingly complemented the Turning Land into Capital policy. International (development partner) organizations like the World Bank or the Green Climate Fund (which coordinates climate finance within the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change; e.g., reducing emissions from deforestation and forest degradation [REDD+]) account for the most important strategic proponents of these strategies. In the course of the Green Growth Development Policy Operation, for example, the World Bank has provided budget support, with payments, depending on the establishment of certain green growth policies: timber legality through Forest Law Enforcement, Governance, and Trade (FLEGT) in 2018, the establishment of Laos' largest national park, Nakai-Nam Theun Park, in 2019, and the adoption of the new Forestry Law in 2020 (FAO 18 Feb 2020, World Bank 5 March 2020, Vientiane, *personal communication*). In Laos, the National Institute for Economic Research has served as the focal point for establishing a national Green Growth Strategy: the sustainable intensification of agriculture as well as increasing forest cover through tree plantations represent the most important pillars to link economic and environmental interests in the Lao Green Growth Strategy (GoL 2018).

Contrary to the earlier moratoria on rubber and eucalyptus, PM Order 9 in 2018 and the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry's Ministerial Instruction 1758 in 2019 opened 600,000 ha of degraded state forest land within National Production Forest Areas for private tree plantations (especially eucalyptus and acacia). This corresponds to an area larger than what has already been granted to date for agriculture and tree plantations combined. The contradictory handling of eucalyptus plantations illustrates the controversial debate on related benefits and risks: while eucalyptus apparently grows on degraded forest land and can be harvested after a short time, it also adversely affects the local water balance and poses the risk of encroachment on better land (Baird 2014).

METHODS

Data

We quantified biomass carbon emissions caused by land concessions in Laos in the period 2001–2017. To this end, we combined the recent inventory of “Land leases and concessions in the Lao PDR” (Hett et al. 2020) with national land cover maps and information on biomass carbon densities in different land use categories. In addition to investigating national-level trends, we took a closer look at two provinces, one in the north (Luang Namtha), and one in the south (Champasak), where large areas have been developed into concessions. Our analysis included all concessions already developed in agriculture, tree plantation, and mining subsectors (878 deals, 525,890 ha), but excluded projects that have not started (yet), that ceased operation during the contract period, that concluded contract and operation, or for which the exact location is unknown (327 deals, 42,160 ha). Hydropower concessions and contract farming are not part of this analysis either.

We quantified the emissions caused by concessions as the difference in biomass stocks before and after the implementation of each concession. To this end, we combined spatially explicit data on concessions granted, developed, and abandoned between 1993 and 2017 that were surveyed for the national inventory of land concessions (Hett et al. 2020) and had national land cover data available for five points in time (DoF 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020; see also Table A1.1). While the accuracy of the national land cover data sets was arguably limited, we considered it suitable and of sufficient quality for our analysis for two major reasons. Firstly, differences to other, larger scale land cover data sets of the region (e.g., Kang et al. 2019) result partly from differences in methodological approaches. The national land cover data set used here relies on visual interpretation of remote sensing data (see Table A1.1) rather than on machine learning. Results are less standardized than those from machine-learning approaches, but this method allows for context-dependent interpretation and is thus suitable for processing data on complex tropical land use systems like the ones in Laos (Leisz et al. 2005). Secondly, an accuracy assessment performed by the Lao Department of Forestry for the 2019 land cover data set (DoF 2020) indicated that the overall accuracy of classification among all classes was 79.8%, but the accuracy of classification as forest versus non-forest was 93.1%. This means that the classification that is most relevant for carbon stocks, and thus for our analysis, is quite accurate. Table A1.2 additionally states the level of accuracy for each land cover category, according to the Lao Department of Forestry (DoF 2020).

By integrating land cover data and data on land concessions, we created matrices that quantified concession-related land conversions in four time periods: 2001–2005, 2006–2010, 2011–2015, and 2016–2019. The concession-related land conversion matrices contained 18–19 categories of previous land cover (aggregation of two categories in 2015–2019), identical to national forest inventories, and 17 categories of subsequent concessions (Table A1.2). In the last time period between 2016 and 2019, the inventory provided information on concession development only until 2017, which led to an underestimation of land use change during that period.

Table 1. C density values of above and below ground biomass of different land-use categories

Land use category	C density (AGB, BGB) [†] (Mg C/ha)	Region/regional conditions	Source
Rubber	29.8	Laos	Bruun et al. (2018)
Eucalyptus	50.0	Southern China	Du et al. (2015)
Sugarcane	14.8	Southern Brazil	Bordonal et al. (2017)
Pasture	3.1	Moist tropical	IPCC (2006)
Coffee	12.8	Costa Rica	Hergoualc'h et al. (2012)
Jatropha	7.0	Mexico	Skutsch et al. (2011)
Oranges	76.3 [‡]	Ghana	Kongsager et al. (2013)
Evergreen forest	200.0–205.8	Laos	DoF and JICA (2017), DoF (2020)
Mixed deciduous forest	87.7–87.9	Laos	DoF and JICA (2017), DoF (2020)
Dry dipterocarp forest	43.2–50.8	Laos	DoF and JICA (2017), DoF (2020)
Other forest	24.4–92.6	Laos	IPCC (2003), DoF and JICA (2017), DoF (2020)
Regenerating vegetation	10.4–17.4	Laos	DoF (2018, 2020)
Grassland, savannah, scrub	3.1–30.0	(Moist) tropical	IPCC (2003, 2006)
Agriculture categories	2.6–5.0	Moist tropical	IPCC (2003)

[†] C density of aboveground (AGB) and belowground biomass (BGB). Soil organic carbon excluded.

[‡] C density of aboveground biomass only.

Quantification of carbon emissions from land conversion

In order to quantify the biomass carbon emissions from concession development in Laos, we followed IPCC guidelines (IPCC 2006, 2019) and applied a stock-difference approach, quantifying the difference between biomass carbon stocks in aboveground and belowground vegetation before and after a concession was implemented, and divided the stock difference by the number of years between two time points to infer annual net carbon fluxes (see Appendix 2). We display all carbon fluxes in t CO₂e yr⁻¹, with positive values indicating emissions to the atmosphere (i.e., decreasing biomass carbon stocks) and negative values indicating carbon sequestration in biomass (i.e., decreasing biomass carbon stocks). Due to a lack of consistent data on soil organic carbon, an ecosystem carbon pool larger but less dynamic than biomass, our analysis is restricted to carbon fluxes from biomass.

We quantified biomass carbon pools in each land cover category by applying specific values for biomass carbon density (Mg C/ha) to the area of the respective category. Carbon density values of aboveground and belowground biomass were derived from the literature, using country-specific values wherever available (Table 1). For tree plantations, we used time-averaged carbon density values that reflected the typical mean stand age of plantations. While these data provided valuable information on the typical carbon density of the respective land use categories, data robustness was limited due to several factors: (1) use of mean rotation periods instead of exact stand ages, (2) non-consideration of soil degradation in our data set, (3) lack of country-specific data for certain land use types (see Table 1), and (4) use of national averages, which ignored regional deviations (Gibbs et al. 2007, Hett et al. 2011). Focusing on (1), we conducted a sensitivity analysis using minimum and maximum carbon density values reported in the literature for the categories with the most variable carbon densities to quantify the effect of data uncertainty on our major results (see Appendix 3). For land cover, the most critical category was regenerating vegetation, which corresponded to shifting cultivation fallows, and for concessions, the most crucial categories were rubber and eucalyptus plantations.

We compared our results to national emissions from all other land conversions (Bauernschuster et al. 2022) to investigate the changing role of concessions in the national carbon budget of land conversions in Laos.

RESULTS

Concessions as drivers of land use change

Between 2001 and 2017, an area of 526,248 ha, or 2% of the total land area in Laos, was converted into agricultural and tree plantations and mining sites (Fig. 2), which corresponded to roughly 12% of all land conversions that occurred during this period and approximately 52% of all concessions granted. Mixed deciduous forest and regenerating vegetation were the land cover categories most affected, and accounted for 33% and 32% of total concession-related land conversions, respectively (Fig. 2). Both of these land cover categories are associated with shifting cultivation fallows: regenerating vegetation contains young fallows (< 7 years), and mixed deciduous forest at least partly includes older fallows (7+ years) (DoF 2018). Other important land cover categories affected by land concessions included dry dipterocarp forest (13%), agricultural land (10%) such as rice paddies, and evergreen forest (5%).

A concession boom can be observed between 2001 and 2010 (402,226 ha), but it significantly slowed down between 2011 and 2017 (124,022 ha) (Fig. 3). The period of most pronounced concessions expansion was 2006–2010 (290,284 ha). The decline in new concessions after 2010 was due mainly to an almost complete end of tree plantations, and was accompanied by an increasing relative relevance of mining concessions toward the end of the investigation period. In 2016–2017, mining was the only subsector that recorded an increase in new concessions (63,064 ha) and constituted 96% of developed concessions in that period. Throughout the time between 2001 and 2017, mining concessions amounted to almost half (47%) of the total area converted into concessions (249,955 ha).

Tree plantations, predominantly rubber and eucalyptus (in sum, 95% of tree plantations), constituted the second largest share of concession area (38% or 198,320 ha). They dominated concession development during the boom period between 2001 and 2010,

Fig. 2. Cumulated land conversions to concessions between 2000 and 2017.

Fig. 3. Land concessions expansion and its share in total land conversions.

and amounted to 48% of total concession area (Fig. 3). Tree plantation development declined after 2010 even more steeply than mining concessions and made up only 4% of concessions or 5086 ha in 2011–2017.

Agricultural plantations constituted the smallest share (15% or 77,973 ha) of concession area. After a slow start in 2001–2005, a boom of land conversions into cash crop plantations such as sugarcane (32,282 ha), coffee (11,849 ha), and jatropha (2391 ha), as well as cattle grazing areas (10,567 ha), took place in 2006–2010, which superseded earlier fruit tree plantations (2256 ha in 2001–2005) (Fig. 3). Agricultural plantation development declined between 2011 and 2015 (27,424 ha), and vanished almost completely in 2016–2017 (2292 ha).

Concessions as drivers of carbon emissions

The development of mining concessions, tree plantations, and agricultural plantations in Laos resulted in average land use change-induced emissions of 4.9 Mt CO₂e yr⁻¹ in the period 2001–2017. Concessions were thus responsible for 34% of emissions from land conversions in the country (Bauernschuster et al. 2022). Per unit of land converted, concessions caused emissions of 257 t CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ as compared to the national average excluding concessions of 47 t CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹.

In 2001–2005, emissions from concession development (1.4 Mt CO₂e yr⁻¹) were lower than the interannual average because the area expansion of concessions was small, and tree and agricultural plantations resulted in modest net carbon sinks, which slightly counterbalanced emissions from mining development (Fig. 4). In 2006–2010, both the area under new concessions and the carbon lost per area under new concession increased dramatically, which resulted in emissions of 7.0 Mt CO₂e yr⁻¹. In 2011–2015, emissions from concession development were 1.8 Mt CO₂e yr⁻¹, particularly because of the reduced mining development. In 2016–2017, mining development increased again and resulted in net emissions of 9.5 Mt CO₂e yr⁻¹ (99.8% of concession-related emissions emerged from mining).

Conversions of forests, especially mixed deciduous forest, evergreen forest, and dry dipterocarp forest, into concessions caused the largest gross and net emissions between 2001 and 2017 (Fig. 5a). Conversions into mining concessions (4487 kt CO₂e yr⁻¹) dominated these emissions, followed by tree and agricultural plantations (104 kt CO₂e yr⁻¹ and 326 kt CO₂e yr⁻¹, respectively). The largest gross sinks, on the other hand, occurred due to conversions of regenerating vegetation (266 kt CO₂e yr⁻¹), agricultural land (143 kt CO₂e yr⁻¹), and grassland (31 kt CO₂e yr⁻¹) into rubber (215 kt CO₂e yr⁻¹), eucalyptus (198 kt CO₂e yr⁻¹), and fruit tree plantations (18 kt CO₂e yr⁻¹) (Fig. 5b).

Fig. 4. Net emissions of land conversions in Mt CO₂e / yr from 2000–2017 (concession and non-concession area).

Fig. 6 shows the carbon emission intensity of land conversions; i.e., the amount of carbon emitted or sequestered per unit land, according to the different concession types, as well as all other land conversions outside of concessions (Bauernschuster et al. 2022). Conversions into concessions showed a significantly higher average carbon emission intensity (256 t CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) than the national average of emissions from land conversions excluding concessions across the total time period (47 t CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹). From 2016 to 2017, the period of the highest emissions from concessions, land conversions into concessions resulted in 69% of net emissions from land conversions but accounted for only 7% of all land conversions (Fig. 3, Fig. 6), caused by the high carbon-emission intensity of mining concessions.

Across concession types, mining concessions were responsible for the highest net carbon emissions by far (4487 kt CO₂e yr⁻¹ or 91%), which exceeded the emissions from the other concession subsectors by a factor of 10 (430 kt CO₂e yr⁻¹ or 9%) (Fig. 5a). Mining concessions continued to cause high emissions even after the boom period of 2006–2010 (Fig. 4); 94% of those emissions occurred due to conversions from different forest types, especially mixed deciduous and evergreen forest. In terms of area, a large amount of regenerating vegetation was also converted to mining lands. In addition to eliminating carbon stocks in forest ecosystems, mining concessions resulted in no carbon sinks to balance the losses from land conversions because the typical open-pit mining sites allow for no vegetation cover (Delang et al. 2013).

Conversion to tree plantations caused both emissions and sinks, with a net effect amounting to carbon emissions of 104 kt CO₂e yr⁻¹ or 2% of total concession emissions (Fig. 5b). Whether tree plantations act as emissions or sinks of carbon depends on the difference in carbon stocks between previous and succeeding land cover, and the two major tree plantations species show diverging effects: rubber has, on average, a lower carbon density than eucalyptus, and land concessions for rubber affected mostly mixed deciduous forests, a land cover class of comparatively high carbon density. This effect resulted in rubber concessions causing net emissions of 218 kt CO₂e yr⁻¹ in 2001–2017. Conversions into eucalyptus, on the other hand, affected land cover categories of lower carbon densities such as regenerating vegetation, and

resulted in net sinks of 137 kt CO₂e yr⁻¹. Overall, the emissions of rubber expansion were greater than the sinks caused by eucalyptus plantations. Those emissions, however, are subject to high uncertainty because the carbon densities both before land conversions, due to a high share of regenerating vegetation, and after land conversion may vary greatly depending on the respective rotation period, for which robust data are not available. Results of a sensitivity analysis are presented in the *Discussion: Limitations* section.

Conversions to agricultural plantations resulted in net carbon emissions that were approximately three times the emissions from tree plantations (326 kt CO₂e yr⁻¹ or 7% of total concession emissions). This was because agricultural plantations, on average, have low carbon stocks but replaced forest ecosystems with higher carbon stocks. Conversions into agricultural plantations affected mainly mixed deciduous and dry dipterocarp forests; this resulted in a large amount of gross emissions in 2001–2017 (351 kt CO₂e yr⁻¹), which by far offset the modest gross sinks related to conversions of rice paddy and other agriculture into agricultural plantations (-23 kt CO₂e yr⁻¹) (Fig. 5b).

Regional divergences

Due to geographic differences, including diverging topography, varying degrees of infrastructure development, and heterogeneous demographic structures, we observed differences in the context and nature of concessions in different parts of the country.

Luang Namtha Province

Luang Namtha Province (9534 km²) is located in Northern Laos bordering China (Fig. 1). Evergreen and mixed deciduous forest cover almost 60% of its area, followed by regenerating vegetation (30%), and agricultural land (9%). In 2011, agricultural households accounted for 80–90% of all households in the province, and shifting cultivation was practiced widely (Epprecht et al. 2018), despite efforts at reduction and replacement (with rubber), for example, in the course of China's opium replacement program (Lu 2017).

Concessions in Luang Namtha add up to approximately 2.5% of the total land area in the province (Fig. 1). The concessions almost exclusively comprise rubber plantations (95%) and a small area of mining concessions (5%). Nearly half of all area converted into concessions was originally regenerating vegetation, followed by mixed deciduous forest, which resulted in net emissions in 2001–2017 of 91 kt CO₂e yr⁻¹. Emission intensity of concession development in Luang Namtha increased drastically in 2016–2017 when emissions from mining concessions, which affected only 20 ha, exceeded those from tree plantations.

Champasak Province

Champasak Province (14,978 km²) is located in Southern Laos (Fig. 1). Here, 71% of the land is covered by evergreen, mixed deciduous, and dry dipterocarp forests, followed by agricultural land (18%) and regenerating vegetation (4%). The fertile Bolaven Plateau, located in Champasak, produces 58% of all coffee in Laos (Delang et al. 2013, Epprecht et al. 2018).

The concession landscape in Champasak differs from Luang Namtha's in many aspects: concessions add up to 5% of the total land area and show great diversity (Table 2). While rubber plays a dominant role here, too (30,000 ha or 39% of the total developed area in the province), dozens of other products are also produced in concessions, such as bauxite in the mining sector (25% of total

Fig. 5. Emissions of concession development 2000–2017 in Mt CO₂e/yr: (a) all concessions (b) tree and agricultural plantations only (SC: shifting cultivation; e: gross emissions to the atmosphere; s: gross sinks in biomass).

Fig. 6. Emission intensity of land conversions in t CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (concession and non-concession area) and share of concession-induced emissions in total emissions of land conversions.

concession area), and coffee (15%), sugarcane (11%), cattle (2%), and rice (2%), followed by a variety of more than 20 different fruit trees, vegetables, and livestock concessions in the agricultural sector. More than half of the developed concession area was originally forest, 25% was regenerating vegetation, and 18% was agricultural land and rice paddy, which resulted in net emissions in 2001–2017 of 425 kt CO₂e yr⁻¹.

DISCUSSION

Concession development in Laos in the past 20 years resulted in net carbon emissions of 4.9 Mt CO₂e yr⁻¹. While concession development represents a relatively small share of domestic land conversions (12%), it caused a large share of land use change-induced emissions (34%). Concession development is thus characterized by an emission intensity that is seven times as high as that of other land conversions.

Limitations

The validity of our findings critically relies on the quality of the empirical input data, as well as on the chosen system boundaries.

Table 2. Concession area and emissions in Luang Namtha (L) and Champasak (C)

	2001–2005		2006–2010		2011–2015		2016–2017	
	L	C	L	C	L	C	L	C
Mining (ha)	425	–	558	14,775	175	4,423	20	25
Tree plantations (ha)	1,900	18,865	20,336	11,944	138	95	–	15
Agriculture (ha)	–	948	23	15,019	–	10,346	–	630
Emissions (kt CO ₂ e/yr)	39	67	322	948	2	646	3	16
Emission intensity (t CO ₂ e/ha/yr)	17	3	15	23	8	44	123	59

Restricting the analysis to carbon fluxes from biomass, while excluding soil organic carbon, increases the robustness but also limits the scope of our study. Limited evidence of soil organic carbon change due to the expansion of tree plantations is available for Northern Laos (Bruun et al. 2018, 2021) and neighboring Yunnan (de Blécourt et al. 2013). Those studies found that the development of rubber plantations was associated with steep losses in soil organic carbon when compared to shifting cultivation systems or other secondary forests. This suggests that our results are a conservative estimate of the emissions impact of land concessions expansion in Laos.

Data uncertainties pertain to our analysis, specifically with regard to the extent (see *Methods*) and carbon density of regenerating vegetation, and the carbon density of tree plantations. To quantify the impact of the latter on our results, we conducted a sensitivity analysis by applying minimum and maximum values of carbon density from the literature to the most crucial land categories of regenerating vegetation, rubber, and eucalyptus plantations, and by assuming high and low values representing long and short rotation periods (see Appendix 3). The analysis showed that depending on the assumptions of rotation lengths in regenerating vegetation and tree plantations, tree plantations may have acted as even stronger sources of carbon emissions (9.2 Mt CO₂e yr⁻¹) but also as carbon sinks (-2.9 Mt CO₂e yr⁻¹) when compared to our best guess estimate of 0.1 Mt CO₂e yr⁻¹ in 2001–2017. The uncertainty about rotation lengths of shifting cultivation fallows and, to a lesser extent, tree plantations thus impeded our ability to draw definite conclusions about the emissions impacts of tree plantations, and about concession development on shifting cultivation fallows. The results of our analysis underscore calls for improved data availability regarding the actual rotation periods and carbon densities in tree plantations and shifting cultivation lands (Mertz et al. 2021). However, our data show that uncertainties are not large enough to reverse the general finding that concession development in general caused significant net carbon emissions across the entire 2001–2017 period.

Policy implications: land acquisitions and sustainable land use

Our results show that despite green intentions of policy-makers, concessions in the Lao People’s Democratic Republic resulted in net carbon emissions because they were characterized mainly by low carbon density and were established mainly in carbon-rich forest ecosystems, even if such land was classified as degraded land. To mitigate the adverse impacts on carbon emissions and local livelihoods of future land acquisitions, policy options include (a) a reduction in land acquisitions as the most emissions-intensive type of land conversion, and (b) the minimization of emissions and social conflict induced by granted concessions, which differ across concession types.

To reduce land acquisitions, the Government of Laos recently started to impose moratoria on rubber, eucalyptus, and mining concessions after having promoted land concessions for these activities since 2000. Promotion and moratoria of certain land deals are reflected in the boom and bust of Laos’s concession development and the peak in emissions in 2006–2010. However, continued development of mining sites even after moratoria indicates the long-lasting impacts of concessions once granted due to time lags between the grant of a concession and the development of the respective activity. For example, in 2016–2017, the shortest period analyzed in this study, existing contracts for mining concessions became effective, which resulted in the development of new mining sites and subsequently the highest emissions of all time periods and concession types. Moratoria are an important lever in reducing the adverse effect of land acquisitions, but they become effective only after a certain delay. However, future concessions that provoke further environmental or livelihood conflicts on currently unaffected land might be effectively prevented by moratoria.

In addition, while moratoria take time to reveal effectiveness on the ground, concessions once granted have long-lasting effects far into the future: concessions contracts typically cover up to 70 years, with possible infinite extensions (PM Order 135 in 2009), and were only recently restricted to 50 years (National Assembly 2016). Access restrictions to granted concessions are not lifted by moratoria, so that local people who depend on forest resources for subsistence or sale lose this important food and income source (Broegaard et al. 2017, Keovilignavong and Suhardiman 2020) and are negatively affected by land acquisitions in the long term (Shi 2015, *personal communication*, Nanthavong et al. 2020, Müller et al. 2021). Political maneuvering space regarding existing concession contracts is thus limited. Future concessions, if granted, should be regulated and monitored closely and continuously to ensure their contribution to national development plans and local needs, as well as to assess their long-term environmental impacts, and contracts should allow for termination if they turn out to be destructive (Lay et al. 2021). Investors need to be held accountable for environmental consequences of their land acquisitions, for example, by being obliged to restore land after the end of a concession contract, as is already requested in the Lao Forestry Law (GoL 2007).

To minimize the environmental and social impacts induced by land concessions, Lao land use and development policies have focused on degraded land (GoL 2005:11, National Assembly 2007, 2019). However, there is no consensus among different stakeholders on its definition. For example, land zoned as degraded by government authorities is often not perceived as degraded by users of that land (Lestrelin 2010, Baird 2014). Land

degradation appears to be a concept used by authorities and investors to justify the development of concessions on certain land (mostly shifting cultivation fallows, as our data show) and thereby restrict access by previous land users. However, if that land were actually degraded, concessionaires would show no interest, and successful operation of plantations would be highly unlikely (Baird 2014). Our results confirm that such lands may host carbon-rich ecosystems. The concession landscape on the Bolaven Plateau (5% of total land) in Champasak, for example, shows how investors are eager to get hold of the fertile and resource-rich land, which by no means had been degraded but was used particularly by smallholding coffee farmers before tens of thousands of hectares were transformed to rubber, coffee, and bauxite concessions (Delang et al. 2013).

Allocation of land classified as degraded to investors indicates a preference for plantations at the expense of smallholding farmers and shifting cultivators based on the assumption that their practices are unproductive, and in the case of shifting cultivation, destructive and cause emissions. Such generalized narratives consider neither any positive impacts of shifting cultivation (for biodiversity, or conservation of soil organic carbon stocks) (Scheidel and Work 2018, Bruun et al. 2021), nor the emission intensity of the practice compared to the high emission intensity of many land concessions demonstrated in this study. Instead, the carbon sequestration potential of the preferred tree plantations is likely overestimated. Moreover, the much lower carbon sequestration potential of agricultural plantations compared to young and old fallows, as well as hidden emissions related to more industrialized, intensified land use, are mostly neglected or quietly accepted (Scheidel 2018, Gingrich et al. 2019). Our findings highlight that the degraded land classification is not suited to identifying areas of low carbon density. Instead of relying on a vague, normative classification, a more data-based classification of land in terms of carbon density is an immediate prerequisite for policies to identify locations for plantations where the emissions impact is low.

Options for minimizing negative social and ecological impacts of future land deals differ across concessions types. Mining concessions depend on resource deposits and have to be allocated to resource-rich locations, causing emissions or social conflicts, or not granted at all. Agricultural and tree plantations, on the other hand, are not constrained to a specific location. In the case of new deals, such as the opening of 600,000 ha of land for private tree plantations (*Introduction: From Turning Land into Capital*), considering location flexibilities of concessions can mitigate some adverse social and ecological impacts. In fact, Lao land use policies (GoL 2005:11, National Assembly 2007, 2019) already focus their development efforts on unused or degraded land. However, despite Laos' low population density and myth of vast empty land, most land is used by people with "land-extensive lifestyles (shifting cultivation, cattle raising in pastures or forests, and the collection of forest products)" (Delang et al. 2013:151). Research has shown that not much land is available for investment without displacing current land users (Kenney-Lazar et al. 2018). Allocating land under use to concessionaires poses the risk that displaced land users either shorten fallow periods of remaining fallows and intensify land use with possibly land-degrading impacts (Ducourtieux and Castella 2006, Martin et al. 2018), or encroach on previously forested land (Zaehring et al. 2018), both of which result in carbon emissions.

In terms of their climate impacts, agricultural and tree plantations will cause the least emissions if the area where they are granted has lower carbon densities than the subsequent plantation. For agricultural plantations, this means that, with the exception of permanent crops such as fruit trees, expansion of agricultural plantations will either cause emissions when areas under no or very extensive use are cleared, or affect land already cleared and under other use; e.g., for smallholder agriculture. By contrast, climate change-mitigating effects of tree plantations can be achieved if (a) the plantations are characterized by high carbon density, like eucalyptus plantations (Du et al. 2015), and (b) they are established in land with low or modest carbon stocks, such as actually degraded forest, grassland, or agricultural land; this, however, risks socioeconomic trade-offs (Kongsager et al. 2013, Liao et al. 2021). Free, prior, informed consent and inclusion of smallholder farmers from the earliest planning stages should be a prerequisite for any new concession contracts in order to potentially mitigate negative consequences for local communities (Lay et al. 2021).

CONCLUSION

The development of land concessions in Laos over the past 20 years caused carbon emissions and has long-term implications for local livelihoods. Striving for socially and ecologically just development, the Government of Laos will have to consider carefully which locations for and species of future plantations cause the least harm to local communities and carbon budgets. If mining concessions are granted, compensation measurements such as afforestation should be set in place to offset emissions that are induced by land use conversions into sites with no inherent capacity for carbon storage. When allocating land for the 600,000 ha of tree plantations in the course of Laos' green growth strategy, the Government of Laos should make every effort to prevent land use competition. If land use competition cannot be avoided, the Government of Laos should offer genuine consultation and acquire free, prior, and informed consent of all affected land users in order to potentially mitigate negative impacts of land acquisitions. If concessions are granted, communities should be provided sufficient compensation for lost land and resources. Not granting new concessions and shifting away from land-sparing approaches toward an acceptance of multifunctional landscapes are also options within the political maneuvering space that have potentially positive social and environmental outcomes.

[1] The terms "concession" and "land acquisition" are used interchangeably in this article.

Responses to this article can be read online at:
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Data Availability:

The data presented in this analysis are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5797965>

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Appendix 1

Table A1.1 satellite images underlying the land cover dataset

Name	SPOT4 / 5 MS	RapidEye	RapidEye	Sentinel-2
Forest Type Map	2005	2010	2015	2019
Observation term	From Oct. 2004 to Apr. 2006	From Nov. 2010 to Mar. 2011	From Nov. 2014 to Feb. 2015	From Jan. 2019 to Mar. 2019
Number of scene	114	146	94	229
Spatial resolution	10m	5m	5m	10m
Bands	Band1: Green Band2: Red Band3: NIR Band4: SWIR	Band1: Blue Band2: Green Band3: Red Band4: Red edge Band5: NIR	Band1: Blue Band2: Green Band3: Red Band4: Red edge Band5: NIR	Band2: Blue Band3: Green Band5: Red Band8: NIR Band11: SWIR

We generate matrices which show land conversions in four time periods from 2001-05, 2006-10, 2011-15 and 2016-17. They contain 18-19 categories of former land use (also used in national forest inventories; aggregation of two categories in 2016-17, see Table A1.1), and 3 categories of subsequent concessions, namely tree plantations, agricultural plantations, and mining.

Table A1.2 Land cover and concessions categories

Land cover categories	Accuracy (DoF, 2020)	Concessions categories
Evergreen Forest	99.5%	Tree plantations
Mixed Deciduous Forest	93.6%	Rubber
Dry Dipterocarp Forest	81.3%	Eucalyptus
Coniferous Forest	100.0%	“Other” tree plantations
Mixed Coniferous and Broadleaved Forest	100.0%	
Forest Plantation	43.2%	

Bamboo	90.0%	Agricultural plantations
Regenerating Vegetation	63.7%	Cashew nuts
Savannah		Cassava
Scrub		Corn/Maize
Grassland		Sugarcane
Swamp		Cattle and buffalo
Upland Crop		Coffee
Rice Paddy		Jatropha
Other Agriculture		Mangoes
(Agricultural Plantations)		Oranges
Urban		“Other” agricultural plantations
Barren Land and Rock		
Other Land		Mining

We divide the categories “tree plantation” and “agricultural plantation” into sub-categories according to most common concessions set out in the inventory of land leases and concessions in Laos (Hett et al., 2020). We assume that land use under mining does not differ significantly between different mining products and therefore forego the subdivision of this category.

In order to produce said land-use change matrices we combined spatially explicit, nationwide data on concessions surveyed for the inventory of land leases and concessions in Laos (Hett et al., 2020) with national land cover data (DoF, 2015, 2010, 2005, 2000). This enables us to compare pre- and post-concession land uses: we compare concession-related land conversions in the respective time periods (2001-05, 2006-10, 2011-15, 2016-17) when the concessions have been approved with former land use at the same geographic location in the base years 2000, 2005, 2010 and 2015. 328 Land deals without known geographic location had to be excluded from analysis.

Figures A1.1-A1.4 display cumulated concession-related land conversions for the time periods 2001-2005 (Fig. A1.1), 2006-2010 (Fig. A1.2), 2011-2015 (Fig. A1.3), and 2016-2017 (Fig. A1.4).

Figure A1.1) Land conversions in 2001-2005

Figure A1.2) Land conversions in 2006-2010

Figure A1.3) Land conversions in 2011-2015

Figure A1.4) Land conversions in 2016-2017

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Appendix 2

Forests, grassland, agricultural land

C stock values for different forest, grassland and agricultural land categories are adopted from a range of national reports and IPCC guidelines, see Table A2.1 below.

Table A2.1: C stock values of forest, grassland, and agricultural land categories

Land-use category	2001-2015		2016-2017	
	Mg C/ha	Source	Mg C/ha	Source
Evergreen Forest	200.0	DoF and JICA, 2017	205.8	DoF, 2020
Mixed Deciduous Forest	87.7	DoF and JICA, 2017	87.9	DoF, 2020
Dry Dipterocarp Forest	43.2	DoF and JICA, 2017	50.8	DoF, 2020
Coniferous Forest	92.6	DoF and JICA, 2017	77.1	DoF, 2020
Mixed coniferous and broadleaved forest	114.7	DoF and JICA, 2017	87.6	DoF, 2020
Forest plantations	37.2	IPCC, 2003 (Annex 3A.1; table 3A.1.6)		
Bamboo	24.4	DoF, 2018 (Annex 2)		
Regenerating vegetation	17.4	DoF, 2018 (Annex 2)	10.4	DoF, 2020
Savannah	11.9	IPCC EFDB; ID 513130		
Scrub	30.0	IPCC, 2006 (Vol. 4, Chapter 4, table 4.7)		
Grassland	3.1	IPCC, 2003 (Chapter 3, table 3.4.2)		
Upland Crop	5.0	IPCC, 2003 (Chapter 3, table 3.3.8)		
Rice Paddy	5.0	IPCC, 2003 (Chapter 3, table 3.3.8)		
Other Agriculture	2.6	IPCC, 2003 (Chapter 3, table 3.3.4)		
Agricultural plantations	30.0	IPCC EFDB; ID 511318		

Tree and agricultural plantations

Table A2.2 lists all C stock values of different plantation types we derived from the literature.

Table A2.2: C stock values of different plantation categories

Land-use category	Mg C/ha	Source
Forest plantations		
Rubber	29.8	Bruun et al., 2018
Eucalyptus	50.0	Du et al., 2015
Other tree plantations	24.2	Hergoualc'h and Verchot, 2011
Agricultural plantations		
Cashew nuts	30.0	IPCC EFDB; ID: 511318
Cassava	4.7	IPCC, 2019 (Volume 4, Chapter 5, table 5.9)
Corn/Maize	4.7	IPCC, 2019 (Volume 4, Chapter 5, table 5.9)
Sugarcane	14.8	Bordonal et al., 2017
Cattle and buffalo (grassland)	3.1	IPCC, 2003 (Chapter 3, table 3.4.2)
Coffee (monoculture)	12.8	Hergoualc'h et al., 2012
Jatropha	7.0	Skutsch et al., 2011
Mangoes	76.3	Kongsager et al., 2013
Oranges	76.3	Kongsager et al., 2013
Other agricultural plantations	30.0	IPCC EFDB; ID 511318

We derive time-averaged C stock values (29.8 Mg C ha⁻¹) of **Rubber** plantations from Bruun et al. (2018) who analyzed C stock changes due to conversions of shifting cultivation systems into rubber plantations in Northern Laos. This sort of conversion is very common in Laos.

Whenever possible we use time-averaged C stock values¹. However, when time-averaged values are unavailable, we choose C stock values that reflect the typical mean stand age of

¹ “The carbon storage potential of rotational land use systems like swidden agriculture and rubber plantations is not determined by the carbon stock at any point in time, but by the average amount of carbon stored in the system during its entire rotation – referred to as the time-averaged carbon stock” (Bruun et al., 2018, p. 240).

plantations (e.g. C stock of 4-year-old Eucalyptus plantation with a harvesting period of 7-8 years).

C stock values of **Eucalyptus** plantations vary most among the tree plantations values. We choose Du et al.'s C stock values for 4-5-year-old Eucalyptus plantations which is the mean stand age of Eucalyptus plantations in Laos (harvest at around 7 years (Zhou et al., 2017)).

For **Teak, Acacia, Agarwood** and “**other tree plantations**” we allocate time-averaged C stock values from Hergoualc’h and Verchot (2011).

Cassava and **corn** are common annual agricultural concession crops. Following IPCC guidelines, we adopt the default C stock value for annual cropland one year after conversion (IPCC, 2019; table 5.9).

Sugarcane as a perennial crop has a harvesting period of 3-4 years (National Agriculture and Forestry Research Institute, 2003). In order to achieve average C stock values for this 3-4 period we multiplied annual C inputs of 7.4 Mg ha^{-1} with 2 (years mean plantation duration) (Bordonal et al., 2017).

“**Cattle and buffaloes**” as concession category translates into grazing area or grassland after conversion. We therefore use default IPCC estimates for biomass in grassland and multiply it with 0.5 to obtain its C content (IPCC, 2003, table 3.4.2).

Coffee plants are typically pruned after 7 years in order to prevent declining yields (Winston and FAO Regional Office for Asia and the Pacific, 2005). We assume that aboveground biomass remains more or less constant from then on with regular pruning. Therefore, we use Hergoualc’h et al.'s C stock values of 7-year-old monoculture coffee plantations (Hergoualc’h et al., 2012).

Jatropha is a perennial crop for which we use C stock values from Skutsch et al. (2011) for plantations with 10 years stand age.

C stock values for **Orange** plantations are derived from Kongsager et al. (2013) for aboveground biomass in plantations with 25 years stand age. We assume the same values for **Mango** plantations.

For all **other agricultural plantations** (such as cashew nut trees) we allocate default IPCC estimates for biomass in plantations and multiply them with 0.5 to obtain C stock values of 30.0 Mg C ha⁻¹ (IPCC EFDB; ID: 511318).

Mining

Ecosystem C stocks in the typically surface mining sites in Laos are assumed to equal zero (Delang et al., 2013). There might be regenerating vegetation in abandoned mining sites; abandoned mining concessions are, however, marginal in spatial extent and therefore not additionally considered. An overestimation of emissions due to overlooked conversions of mining sites into regenerating vegetation is therefore possible, although probably also marginal.

Limitations

We focus on the C pool in aboveground and belowground biomass. We do not consider C in soils due to limited data availability and reliability on a national scale.

C stock differences

We multiply stock-difference values of land conversions (e.g. conversion of evergreen forest into cassava plantations equal an ecosystem C stock difference of 195 Mg C ha⁻¹) with respective land conversion matrices and achieve C stock difference matrices. We divide the results by 5 (or 2 in case of the last period between 2016-17, the last year investigated in the concession inventory) to achieve annual values, and multiply them with 44/12 to convert the values into Mg CO_{2e} yr⁻¹. Positive values indicate C emissions, negative values indicate C sinks due to the respective land conversions.

Carbon emission intensity of land conversions (concessions and non-concessions)

We compare C emission intensity of land conversions into concessions (net emissions per ha total land per year) with C emission intensity of all other land conversions. Data base for the latter is Bauernschuster et al. (under review).

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Appendix 3

We conduct a sensitivity analysis to quantify the effect of data uncertainty on our major results. For that we use minimum and maximum C density values reported in the literature covering a range of young and old stand ages of the most crucial land use categories “regenerating vegetation”, “rubber” and “eucalyptus plantations”.

Land use category	Min. C density [Mg C / ha] (stand age)	Source	Max. C density [Mg C / ha] (stand age)	Source
Rubber	29 (time-averaged)	Yang et al. 2016	37.6 (time-averaged)	Guillaume et al. 2018
Eucalyptus	26.9 (4 yr.)	Zhou et al. 2017	95.6 (13 yrs.)	Zhou et al. 2017
Regenerating Vegetation	3 (< 5 yrs.)	Ziegler et al., 2012	138 (10-25+ yrs.)	Ziegler et al., 2012

Figure A3.1) Maximum emissions: Impact of the allocation of minimum values to the land-use categories rubber and eucalyptus, and maximum values to “regenerating vegetation” (RV), on C emissions/sinks of tree plantation development in comparison to the time-averaged values used for the main findings.

Figure A3.2) Maximum sink: Impact of the allocation of maximum values to the land-use categories rubber and eucalyptus, and minimum values to “regenerating vegetation” (RV), on C emissions/sinks of tree plantation development in comparison to the time-averaged values used for the main findings.

Figure A3.3) Net maximum-emissions and net maximum-sink scenarios: Impact of aggregated minimum and maximum values of the land-use categories “regenerating vegetation” (RV), rubber, and eucalyptus on C emissions/sinks of overall concession development (tree, agricultural and mining concessions) in comparison to the time-averaged values used for the main findings.

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